

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

**“Teachers' Feedbacking Skills, Students' Motivation,
And Academic Performance of the Selected
Senior High School Students”**

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ABSTRACT

This research study aims to determine the significant relationship between teachers' feedback skills, student's motivation, and the academic performance of the selected senior high school students at Tanauan School of Fisheries. The result of the study can help teachers improve their skills in giving effective feedback to their students and can help students improve their academic performance through motivation and effective feedback. Workshops, surveys, extracurricular activities, and other activities can be proposed that will help teachers to enhance and develop their skills in giving effective and timely feedback to students and to motivate students to improve their academic performance. The respondents of the study were the selected senior high school students of Tanauan School of Fisheries enrolled in the academic year 2023-2024. The researchers were able to enumerate the Grade 11 respondents (74)

and Grade 12 respondents (75) with a total of one hundred forty-nine (149) students.

The researchers used a self-made survey questionnaire to determine the relationship between teachers' feedback skills, student's motivation, and academic performance of selected senior high school students of Tanauan School of Fisheries. The researchers created 41 sets of questions to identify the relationship. The first question is about the academic performance of the senior high school students. The 20 sets of questions determine students' evaluation of Teachers' feedback skills, and the level of Students' Motivation also has 20 sets of questions. To analyze and interpret the data gathered, the researchers used mean and Pearson's r correlation as a statistical tool.

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that there is a significant relationship between the teachers' feedback skills, students' motivation, and student's academic performance of the selected senior high school students of Tanauan School of Fisheries. Furthermore, workshops, surveys and extracurricular activities will improve the educational performance of the students.

Moreover, it is recommended to foster a positive school culture; administrators should value feedback as a crucial tool for students' growth and motivation. Teachers can employ various feedback methods, such as verbal, written, and peer feedback, tailored to students' individual needs. They may provide prompt feedback after students' performance to maintain relevance and effectiveness in promoting motivation, creating a supportive and positive learning environment where students feel valued and respected. Students may communicate their feedback preferences to teachers, including format, frequency, and level of detail, reflecting on strengths and areas for improvement. Future researchers can expand the findings of this study by getting the learners' demographic profile. Parents can also communicate with teachers to share information about their child's preferences and learning needs, fostering a collaborative and supportive learning environment.

Keywords: Teachers' Feedbacking skills, Motivation, Child Preference, Feedback preferences, Academic Performance

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DEDICATION

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especially in financial problems.

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knowledge, determination, support, care,
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We managed to overcome those challenges,
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We dedicate this research study.
to our family, friends, colleagues
and loved ones.

G.L.R

P.L.R

P.J.E.M

S.K.M

V.L.U

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	PAGE
Title Page	i
Acknowledgment	iii
Dedication	iv
Table of Contents	v
List of Tables	viii
Introduction	1
Theoretical Framework	3
Conceptual Framework	5
Research Paradigm	5
Objectives of the Study	6
Statement of the Problem	7
Hypothesis	8
A Review of Related Literature	9
Synthesis	24

Research Design	25
Sampling	26
Respondents of the Study	26
Research Instrument	27
Validity and Reliability	28
Data-Gathering Procedure	28
Ethical Considerations	29
Treatment for Quantitative Data	30
Presentation, Interpretation, and Analysis	33
Conclusions	63
Recommendations	64
REFERENCES	67
APPENDICES	73
A Letter of Validation, Validation Sheet and Revisions	73
B Research Instrument	91
C Result of Pearson's R	93
D Letter for Distribution of Questionnaire and Letter of Approval	100
E Distribution Tables and Computation of Weighted Mean	103
F Computation of Significant Relationship	110
CURRICULUM VITAE	113

List of Tables

Table		Pages
A	Respondents of the study	26
B	Interpretation of Mean Ranges	27
1	Academic Performance	33
2.1	Level of Motivation In terms of Intrinsic Motivation	35
2.2	Level of Motivation In terms of Extrinsic Motivation	38
2.3	Level of Motivation In terms of Fear Motivation	40
2.4	Level of Motivation In terms of Social Motivation	42
3.1	Student's Evaluation of the Teacher's Feedback Skills in terms of Constructive Feedback	45
3.2	Student's Evaluation of the Teacher's Feedback Skills in terms of Formal Feedback	47
3.3	Student's Evaluation of the Teacher's Feedback Skills in terms of Informal Feedback	50
3.4	Student's Evaluation of the Teacher's Feedback Skills in terms of Corrective Feedback	52
4	Significant relationships between students' motivation and academic performance	55
5	Significant relationships between teachers' feedback skills and students' academic performance	57
6	Significant relationships between teachers' feedback skills and students' motivation	59

List of Figures

Figure		Pages
1	Research Paradigm	5

Introduction

Teachers have a crucial role in guiding and shaping students' academic performance and behavior. One of the most critical skills they possess is providing effective feedback. Teachers can motivate their students and help them improve their academic performance by providing feedback. Teachers need to provide clear and constructive feedback to encourage productive student learning. This way, students can identify areas that require further improvement and enhance their learning activities accordingly (Obilor, 2019).

In the classroom, students are mainly focused on academic performance. Some students need to perform better in school; they fear the feedback they will receive and doubt whether the answer is correct or wrong, even knowing the answer (Rone et al., 2023). Students' motivation helps students focus attention on achieving goals. Feedback is the partner of learning and achievement, and it provides added information to fill the gaps between what students understand and what needs to be understood; thus, it is effective for learning. It helps students with the subject matter and guides them in learning (Matthew, 2021). Instructors' Feedbacking capabilities are essential in the student's overall educational performance to offer insights into what is wanted to enhance the overall performance within the subject. Moreover, comments can be used to encourage the students (Maharma & Abusa'aleek, 2022).

Motivated students achieve the potential to find success. In education, motivation helps students to overcome and inspire the challenges students will face (Hawthorne, 2021). Much literature on teachers' feedback shows that feedback significantly affects students' academic performance. Some students earn motivation through the teachers' feedback, depending on whether it is positive or negative feedback. Feedback provides valuable insights to the students. It helps students' educational journey. Feedback takes various forms, such as Written comments, assessments, verbal discussions, and peer evaluations (Bordia, 2022).

Motivation plays a significant role in students' learning process and academic performance. Everyone needs feedback to grow, especially the students (Turda, 2020). A teacher's constructive, evaluative, and corrective feedback is vital to the students and significantly affects their academic performance (Ahmed et al., 2021).

Intrinsic motivation is completing a task without any exchange. Extrinsic motivation is achieving the goal through rewards, praise, and awards. Fear motivation is a fear of doing wrong. It helps motivate a student not to have a failing grade in school. Social motivation encourages interaction among students, inspired by the cooperation of others (Behari, 2021). Teachers' feedback skills are essential for students by giving constructive feedback, which

is an issue that is focused and based on observation. Formal feedback is a type of feedback that is planned and systematically scheduled into the teaching and learning process. Informal feedback is everyday conversations on how work is being done. Corrective feedback is used to help students reduce making errors (FUA, 2023).

The study determines the relationship between teachers' feedback skills, student motivation, and the selected students' academic performance. It also gives teachers insights into students' motivation, how teachers' feedback influences educational performance and recommendations for schools to improve academic performance. Additionally, the study is appropriate to the selected senior high school students of Tanauan School of Fisheries to determine how teachers' feedback is essential to the student's academic performance. Based on the assumption of the researchers, teachers' feedback can be a motivation or not to the students' academic performance.

Theoretical Framework

This study is based on three (3) theories. The first theory is the **Performance Feedback Theory** by Lucas (2021), which is related to the importance of feedback in improving students' academic performance. The second theory is the **Cognitivism Learning Theory** by Feder (2022), which emphasizes critical thinking, problem-solving, and memory to achieve effective

feedback. Lastly, the third theory is the **Motivation Theory** by Sands (2023), which highlights intrinsic and extrinsic motivation that can be achieved through feedback to improve academic performance.

Performance feedback theory (PFT) by Lucas (2021) because the performance feedback theory is the feedback given to a group of people or an organization. It is related to the study because, in school or institution, feedback is essential to the student's performance to know what other skills and knowledge need to be developed. Responsiveness to the teacher-given feedback is also important because the input should not be ignored; it must be applied to improve the student's academic performance.

Another theory on which this study is anchored is **cognitivism**, a learning theory by Feder (2022) because this theory focuses on a person's critical thinking regarding problem-solving and memory. Therefore, to achieve effective feedback, it should be accurate and relevant to guide and encourage students. This theory is aligned with the study of how students should learn by critical thinking, and students could develop their cognitive skills through the teachers' feedback to determine what needs improvement.

There is also a theory on which this study is anchored: the **motivation theory** by Sands (2023). Motivation theory is the study of a person achieving a particular goal through two factors: intrinsic motivation, which is a desire to

achieve personal goals, and extrinsic motivation, which is getting something in return for achieving the goals. This theory supports the study because teachers' feedback can motivate students to improve the student's academic performance. Students can be encouraged by how they will take the teacher's feedback.

Conceptual Framework

The figure below shows the paradigm of the independent study and the relationship of the dependent Variables model that fits the researchers' ideas.

Figure 1: Research Paradigm

Figure 1 shows the Research Paradigm of the study presented in "Teachers' Feedbacking Skills, Students' Motivation and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students at Tanauan School of Fisheries A.Y 2023-2024".

The first box is the independent variable that presents the students' motivation levels: Intrinsic Motivation, Extrinsic Motivation, Fear Motivation, and Social Motivation, and it also shows the student's perceptions of the teacher's feedbacking skills: Constructive Feedback, Formal Feedback, Informal Feedback, and Corrective Feedback. The second box is the dependent variable that presents the Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students at Tanauan School of Fisheries.

Objectives of the Study

This study determines if there is a relationship between teachers' feedback skills, student's motivation, and academic performance, and the researchers want to:

1. To determine the academic performance of the selected senior high school students;
2. To identify the level of motivation of the designated senior high school students;
3. To determine the students' evaluation of the teachers' feedback skills;

4. To identify the significant relationship between students' motivation and academic performance;
5. To recognize the vital connection between teachers' feedback skills and students' academic performance;
6. To determine the relationship between teachers' feedback skills and students' motivation and
7. To propose an action plan to support the teachers' feedback skills and students' motivation.

Statement of the Problem

The study generally aims to determine the relationship between teachers' feedback skills, students' motivation, and the academic performance of selected senior high school students. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the academic performance of the selected senior high school students?
2. What is the level of motivation of the students in terms of:
 - 2.1 intrinsic motivation;
 - 2.2 extrinsic motivation;
 - 2.3 fear motivation; and

2.4 social motivation?

3. What is the student's evaluation of the teacher's feedback skills in terms of:

3.1 constructive feedback;

3.2 formal feedback;

3.3 informal feedback; and

3.4 corrective feedback?

4. Is there a significant relationship between students' motivation and academic performance?
5. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' feedback skills and students' academic performance?
6. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' feedback skills and students' motivation?
7. Based on the study, what action plan can be proposed to support the teachers' feedback skills and students' motivation?

Hypotheses

There was a significant relationship between students' motivation and academic performance.

There was a significant relationship between teachers' feedback skills and students' academic performance.

There was a significant relationship between teachers' feedback skills and students' motivation.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

This study's review of related literature focuses on the Teachers' feedback skills, Students' Motivation, and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students at Tanauan School of Fisheries A.Y 2022-2023.

According to Agoha (2021), feedback is essential to improve the assessment outcomes of the students, and it is valuable for both students and teachers to understand the performance that can close the gap for the learning targets. Also, feedback can provide insights for students and teachers to adjust learning needs through practical strategies to achieve goals. Additionally, students should reflect on using the teacher's feedback to understand better the learning approach to meet the learning objectives. Feedback is consistent with the current understanding and performance of the student learners; it provides information on the actual status of the students and teachers on what they have expected on the prior learning. However, the teacher needs to ensure that the feedback given to the students is perfectly aligned with the assessment practices or performance so that the learners can use the feedback to improve

their performance and use it as motivation. Feedback can be positive or negative, but it can have a beneficial effect on the student learners.

A research study by Bashir et al. (2016) explains that feedback is considered one of the most challenging issues in higher education. Still, it is essential in improving the student's learning process and learning experience. It is vital in facilitating students to develop students while teachers monitor, evaluate, and regulate their learning. Also, it is more effective and valuable from old models to modern feedback delivery. It is an essential skill for teachers in higher education and has a significant influence on the student's learning process that gives a quality of learning.

The latest study by Schwab et al. (2022) reveals that teacher feedback is one of the significant factors for students' academic achievement. Additionally, students get the same amount of feedback on their behavior and educational attainment, but teachers' feedback affects students' well-being. Constructive feedback is a possible way to support classroom interactions. Giving and receiving feedback can influence the students' emotions.

A Research study by Nakhla (2019), reveals the essential issue of the fear of failure in education that can significantly affect how students are motivated and involved in learning. The utilization of Self Determination Theory and giving an analysis by using the cluster analysis reveals the complicated

relations. It states the extrinsic motivation role that it has in mitigation and fear control. The investigation demonstrates the role of fear of failure in teaching and the need to find ways to mitigate this fear to achieve maximum benefit learning environments.

As per Mattson's (2017) findings, feedback is crucial in enhancing writing skills and meeting students' learning expectations. Additionally, it has been observed that the number of errors the students commit decreases when input is given. The teachers' feedback effectively illustrates how well the students have met the standards. Improving the student's overall performance influences how to move forward in the learning process to develop the learning. Feedback and assessment go hand in hand, as teachers use the review to measure the students learning and to provide an idea of what to teach next, giving an estimate and giving feedback to let the students know how they performed.

According to the University of New South Wales (2023), Giving assessment feedback is significant for the students learning; it guides students to the things that need improvement and motivates them; feedback can be beneficial to the students learning if it is constructive, timely, and meaningful, it will encourage the students to think critically about the academic performance and reflect if students should improve it. Feedback should be provided throughout the course, not only at the end of the teaching and learning process,

but practical feedback also helps to guide and adjust the student's learning and accommodate their learning needs; students can become more independent in the work when feedback is unclear, students may not be able to reflect if the response is positive or negative.

Additionally, feedback during lectures is better for identifying and addressing the common issues in students' academic performance to motivate them. Also, using technology to give feedback is helpful to provide automated feedback like voice email when the student's work is read. Moodle and Turnitin are available online tools to provide formative feedback to students. Many tools are available in Moodle, such as voice board and voice presentation, which allow students to choose the time and place to take the assessment and for teachers to deliver immediate feedback.

One early work of Santos (2019) proves that intrinsic motivation plays a vital role in the students' learning and boosts the confidence of the students to improve their academic performance. Intrinsic motivation is not about getting an external reward for every activity. However, it is about the enjoyment and fun of doing the activity because it is internally rewarding and can fulfill personal satisfaction and be intrinsically motivated.

A research study by Price (2017) explains that one of the teachers' concerns is the improvement of the student's academic performance. Teachers

are looking for different ways to ensure the best learning outcomes for the students. Irregular and ineffective feedback cannot improve the student's academic performance. Feedback is any information, process, and activity that enhances the student's learning based on the completed task. To determine the effectiveness of feedback, teachers must build a good relationship between students. Task feedback, process, self-regulation, and self are the four primary levels that impact its effectiveness.

Additionally, in choosing the methods of delivering feedback to the students, teachers must determine the different types of feedback that can develop and enhance the appropriate skills of the students. Understanding the different factors that affect the effectiveness of feedback is essential to improving the student's level of academic performance; receiving effective feedback improves students' motivation. It helps students to be active in the classroom and allows students with lower abilities to perform well in class discussions. Quality feedback enhances the student's critical thinking skills and increases the student's motivation to participate in learning.

One early work by Faulconer et al. (2021) proves that high-quality feedback is vital to the student's success. However, it suggests that students' perceptions and self-regulated behavior do not change by the type of feedback provided. However, the students who received performance-gap input and

positive feedback received a higher grade than those who only received performance-gap feedback; the feedback is viewed as fundamental to the teaching and learning process. All input is designed to meet the high-quality, specific, and actionable criteria.

According to Selvaraj (2021), much literature on teachers' feedback states that feedback dramatically affects the students' academic performance. However, feedback is a challenge for teachers due to the inability of teachers to provide the students with needed feedback for self-improvement. Teachers need to ensure that the feedback will meet the student's academic needs to improve the work after receiving the feedback, it is essential to determine the correlation between teachers' feedback and students' performance and guide them to develop the learning strategies that may help to strengthen the ability of the students. Also, it will provide better learning opportunities while teaching them to overcome weaknesses. In addition, while exploring the connection between the student's academic performance and teachers' feedback, it was discovered that teachers played a significant role in helping students improve their academic performance and motivate them to become independent.

According to a research study mentioned in Ahmed et al.'s (2021) work, feedback from teachers is a crucial aspect that must be considered in the teaching and learning process. It not only motivates students to perform at a

high academic level, but constructive and evaluative feedback also enhances their self-efficacy and encourages them to work harder. Thus, teachers' constructive feedback is vital in improving students' academic performance.

One early Work by Brew et al. (2021) proves that good academic performance is essential to the educational system. There are many factors to be considered that affect academic performance, such as the student's absenteeism, capabilities to study, availability, and accessibility to textbooks; these factors affect the academic performance of students in school. Students who have the ability to study perform better compared to students who have no ability; teachers should monitor and adjust to meet the needs of the students to help improve the academic performance of the students to achieve the goals.

According to the Theory of Performance (ToP) by Elger, humans can accomplish an extraordinary task; ToP creates a framework that can be used to explain the performance and what is needed to improve the performance. People who are more engaged in the collaborative effort can be individual performers or group performers; while developing the performance, it is a journey, and the level of performance is the location that describes the journey.

Additionally, there are six components in the current level of performance, which are the context, level of knowledge, level of skills, level of identity, and personal and fixed factors; also, for the practical improvement of performance,

three axioms are proposed such as the mindset, learn in the changing environment and reflective practice engagement.

According to Wang and Han (2022), feedback plays a crucial role in the writing process. When the COVID-19 pandemic started and rapidly spread worldwide, it brought many challenges, most likely to educational institutions. It led to the teaching and learning process delivered in distance learning, either as blended learning or as pure online, but technology supports education under such circumstances. A web-based automated writing feedback system is a type of online platform that is free and accessible for students to provide immediate feedback. It also helps teachers determine the student's current level of writing ability.

A research study by Zhan (2016) explains that foreign language teachers were suggested to communicate with the students about the feedback that will be given and be aware of the perceptions of the students so the writing instructions can be more effective, written feedback of the teacher plays an important role to improve the students' writing skills that may engage students to take the task seriously. Learners prefer different types of feedback for various reasons because some students need to take the feedback as a severe response. Students received feedback based on content, organization,

vocabulary, grammar, and mechanics. Students learn much from the feedback to improve their learning and writing skills.

One early work by Brookhart (2017) proves that feedback can only lead to learning when the students have opportunities to use it. The best way teachers can help students learn is to guide and build equal opportunities in giving feedback to improve the students learning; modeling is one of the best ways to teach and use feedback as part of the lessons. Feedback intends to be formative, help students learn, and use the feedback in the best way. Feedback is not 'feedback' when it does not feed something, clarify the learning target, or set goals when giving feedback.

According to Nguyen (2019), when teachers give feedback to the students, the effectiveness can be seen in many forms, including the students' proficiency levels, prior learning experiences, expectations, and educational contexts. English writing is challenging for students who want to learn a foreign language to assess the students' teachers' use by indicating the errors using the target language. To improve academic performance, teachers deliver feedback to students in the form of comments, questions, and suggestions on their work. Constructive criticism allows students to revise their work and progress in their studies.

A research study by Victoria University of Wellington (2013) explains that Informal feedback is a formative, confidential method of feedback that can be used for promotion purposes in teaching portfolios and is offered by lecturers and students. Informal feedback is a convenient method for students to provide constructive information, aiding teaching and course delivery. It encourages reflection, suggests skill development, and builds rapport between staff and students, demonstrating the lecturer's concern for their opinions.

According to San Jose Community College (2023), feedback and evaluation are crucial components in the teaching and learning process because they enable the students to understand their prior knowledge and the areas that need development. Formative evaluation takes many forms, including classroom discussion, observations, peer comments, and student self-evaluation. Still, it benefits students, including the ability to provide timely feedback to determine the areas that need improvement faster. Summative evaluation is to evaluate the overall performance of the students; teachers use it to compare the student's performance to the topic or course. These techniques are helpful to give a clear understanding of the student's performance and give students clear feedback and direction.

The latest study by Gou and Zhuo (2021) analyzed gender differences in teacher feedback and students' motivation in learning among 1,082 secondary

students in China. Results showed that male students received less directive feedback but more criticism. Scaffolding feedback and praise is an effective way to cultivate motivation in both male and female students. The study suggests future research and suggestions for teachers to improve motivation.

A study by Strang (2017) investigates the implementation of praise types in a classroom-based action research project. The research used a mixed method constructivist methodology and found that students can be metacognitive about motivation and perceive significant value for process praise. However, the study found that many short-term interventions focus on a short-term basis and do not elicit the cognitive processes that underpin motivation and behavioral change.

One early work by Gentrup et al. (2020) proves that the study found that teacher expectations were somewhat inaccurate, affecting students' learning outcomes. High expectations were associated with better reading and mathematics achievement, while low expectations led to lower reading achievement. Teacher feedback varied with these expectations but did not significantly mediate the effects of teacher expectancy.

According to Johnson (2017), teachers have a vital role in motivating students to learn by providing an autonomy-supportive learning environment and enhancing the autonomy, relevance, and relatedness of the material, especially

in giving positive feedback to motivate the students. Moreover, teachers also have an essential role in increasing students' competence and interest in the material and increasing their self-efficacy. Teachers must develop a motivating learning environment, even if external incentives bring it about. A safe, vibrant setting makes pupils more interactive and engaging with their schoolwork, which causes a more profound comprehension and retention of the material or the subject.

The latest study by Tobgay (2021) reveals that some teachers are experiencing challenges or obstacles in their field of work that make it hard for teachers to create an exciting teaching and learning process. Teachers should understand students to be able to form effective learning. Tobgay (2021) noted that one of the factors that affects the learning process is feedback. In addition, learning outcomes will prove if they dare to act to the teachers given feedback as an opportunity to be motivated to help them achieve good results.

A research study by Carvalho et al. (2014) explains that students' perceptions play an important role in feedback. Students should relate to how they perceive the learnings. However, not all students are influenced by how they perceive the teacher's feedback.

One early work by Gan et al. (2021) proves that the relationship between teacher feedback, students' feedback motivation, and feedback behavior

significantly influences the student's satisfaction with their learning, according to 308 university students. Gan et al. (2021) note that feedback is in various forms because it links teacher teaching methods and students' learning outcomes.

According to Fine et al. (2023), feedback is essential to improve the students' learning and use it as a motivation to acquire knowledge. The students and teachers recognize input because it significantly contributes to understanding.

The latest study by Liu et al. (2022) reveals that when individuals feel they have control over their actions, perceive themselves as competent, and experience a connection with others, they are more likely to thrive and engage in positive behaviors. Various types of motivation for academic performance have been studied in recent decades. Studies have found that intrinsic motivation indicates a positive effect on academic performance, while on the other hand, extrinsic motivation on academic performance plays a more positive effect. However, intrinsic motivation is more relative to all age groups, and extrinsic motivation has a vital influence on students' academic performance as they grow up.

According to The International School of Thrissur (2024), socializing is crucial for student growth, fostering communication skills, empathy, teamwork, diverse perspectives, emotional intelligence, and real-world challenges. It

prepares students with fundamental beliefs, standards, and behaviors for productive participation in society, a process that lasts throughout childhood and adulthood.

One of the early works by Zaccone and Pedrini (2019) proves that the study found that intrinsic motivation contributes to the learning of the students, which drives them to learn effectively, while extrinsic motivation affects the students learning in a negative way that students experience challenges to learn effectively. Students who are intrinsically motivated acquire more knowledge than those who are extrinsically motivated because students are more focused on what to achieve because students are competitive.

A research study by Research Key (2021) explains that Extrinsic motivation comes from external factors like gifts, rewards, giving praises, which provide satisfaction and play a crucial role in impacting the student's academic achievement.

The latest study by Safra et al. (2020) reveals that all humans are inherently social. Social motivation is essential to develop cooperation, trust, and impressions; social motivation helps people to have successful interactions and widen their social circle. Every person has a different preference; trustworthy partners are more cooperative, but some are likely to provide benefits to achieve

successful interaction. Social motivation involves students finding experience and interaction to develop and maintain social bonds.

One early work by Guinness et al. (2020), more than seven meta-analyses conducted in 1980, supports that feedback is the single most powerful tool to improve students' performance. Feedback reinforces to correct students' errors during lessons. A form of feedback used to improve students' achievement and as a teaching technique is corrective feedback.

According to Thomas (2014), fear can act as motivation because when a person fears doing something, the person will think critically before deciding what may help prevent failure and contribute to success. Every student may need to do better at school because fear crashes the student's creativity. Once the students are afraid, it can be used to move away from their comfort zone.

The latest study by Schooley (2023) reveals that informal feedback is spontaneous and less structured because it can be delivered anytime and anywhere. In addition, formal feedback is structured and well-planned. It helps to address employees' strengths and weaknesses to improve performance. Also, formal feedback can be delivered in one-on-one meetings to have privacy when receiving feedback on day-to-day performance.

According to Dela Cruz and Wong (2022), corrective feedback helps to develop the student's critical thinking skills, even if some students prefer oral or written feedback, and positive or negative feedback because it impacts the students' metacognitive skills to a higher level that influences the student's academic performance.

Synthesis

This study is based on various literature that was read and analyzed by the researchers. Agoha and Bashir et al. and Liu et al. both emphasize the importance of teacher feedback in improving students' academic performance. Schooley explains the difference between formal and informal feedback, while Dela Cruz and Wong highlight the benefits of corrective feedback in developing students' metacognitive skills. Brew et al. and the theory of performance of Elger both emphasize the importance of performance in education and to the students or to the performer that develops the performance.

The University of South New Wales stresses the importance of assessment feedback, while San Jose Community College emphasizes the value of formative and summative evaluation in providing precise feedback. Ahmed et al., Strang, Fine et al., Tobgay et al., Gan et al., Guinness et al., and Johnson and Schwab all agree on the significance of feedback in motivating students to improve their learning outcomes. Gou and Zhou have different

opinions on teacher feedback, while Faulconer discusses the benefits of giving performance-gap input and positive feedback. Wang and Han, Zhan, Mattson, and Nguyen stress the importance of proper feedback delivery to improve students' writing skills. Gentrup et al. and Carvalho et al. have different perspectives on the role of feedback in math subjects and learning perception, respectively.

Brookhart, Selvaraj, Victoria University of Wellington, and Price all agree on the importance of teacher feedback in helping students identify weaknesses, achieve learning targets, and improve academic performance. Zaccone and Pedrini, Safra et al., Santos, Research Key, and Thomas have distinct views on intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, social motivation, and fear motivation as motivators for success and failure. All the mentioned authors have different perspectives on the role of feedback, including its benefits in developing metacognitive skills, motivating students to improve their learning outcomes, improving writing skills, and helping students identify weaknesses and achieve learning targets.

Research Design

This study utilized the Quantitative-Correlational research design to determine the relationship between teachers' feedback skills, students' motivation, and students' academic performance. Correlational research design

is a non-experimental research method that examines the relationship between two or more variables. This research design is crucial to determine whether there is a correlation between the variables and the kind of correlation that exists (Pallister, 2023).

Sampling

The researchers used Stratified random sampling; the researchers got the strata per level coming from the whole population of the Senior high school students of the Tanauan School of Fisheries. The researchers randomly chosen from the exact number of respondents needed for the study from the sample size given by the statistician using the random sampling since the respondents have the same attributes and characteristics.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the researchers in this study are the selected Senior High School students of Tanauan School of Fisheries. The researchers utilized the Taro Yamane formula to find the exact number of respondents from the population of senior high school students at Tanauan School of Fisheries. Table A shows the respondents of the study.

Table A
Respondents of the Study

Grade Level	Population size	Sample size
Grade 11	118	74
Grade 12	119	75
Total	237	149

Research Instrument

The researchers used a self-made survey questionnaire to get the data needed for the study. The questionnaires determined the students' perceptions of Teachers' feedback skills and the level of Students' Motivation and academic performance of Selected Senior High School Students at Tanauan School of Fisheries.

The selected senior high school students of Tanauan School of Fisheries answered the following items in the survey questionnaire by rating to what extent using a 4-point rating scale. The responses were four (4) as "Strongly Agree," three (3) as "Agree," two (2) as "Disagree," and one (1) as "Strongly Disagree." The Table B shows the Numerical value, Mean ranges, and Verbal interpretations.

Table B
Interpretation of Mean Ranges

Numerical Value	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretations
4	4.00-3.25	Strongly Agree
3	3.24-2.50	Agree
2	2.49-1.75	Disagree
1	1.74-1.00	Strongly Disagree

Likert Four-Point Scale Range Interpretation (Alico & Guimba, 2015)

Validity and Reliability

The instruments were established for validity and reliability tests. The first draft of the questionnaires was presented to the thesis adviser for comments, suggestions, and corrections. The panel's recommendations and modifications were also considered, to validate the questionnaire. The questionnaire was validated by three validators: Teacher III, Master Teacher I, and Master of Arts in Education from Tanauan City Integrated High School. The researchers asked permission from the principal to conduct a reliability test. To test the reliability of the questionnaire, the researchers conducted a Pre-Test and Post-Test on the thirty (30) randomly selected senior high school students in the Santo Tomas Senior High School since the respondents have the same characteristics and attributes similar to the target respondents of the present study. After answering

and getting the questionnaire, it was forwarded to the statistician to test its reliability. The reliability test result was reliable based on Cronbach's Alpha of internal consistency.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers conducted the study during the School Year 2023-2024 of the Senior High School, involving the following activities: In conducting the study, the researchers prepared a letter of request. The researchers constructed a self-made survey questionnaire, which a panel of experts validated. The researchers used a self-made survey questionnaire that suited the purpose and required data of this study. The researchers asked the respondents to answer the questionnaires honestly to determine the relationship between teachers' feedback skills, student motivation, and the academic performance of selected senior high school students of Tanauan School of Fisheries. After the respondents answered the questionnaire, the researchers asked the statistician to help determine the appropriate statistical tool to use and interpret data. Based on the data, the researchers came up with a conclusion and recommendation for this study. Additionally, before gathering the required data for the study, the researchers implement a pilot test to test the reliability of the questionnaires in Santo Tomas Senior High School.

Ethical Consideration

As the study involved gathering information about the students, it is vital to guarantee their privacy and security. To ensure the confidentiality and consent of the respondents, the researchers provided all the necessary information about the study and its objectives. By doing so, the respondents are able to understand their role in the research and make an informed decision about participating. The researchers also protected the respondents' confidentiality by not revealing their names under the Republic Act 10173- Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

The gathered data underwent the statistical treatment outlined below.

The whole population of senior high school students from Grade 11 and Grade 12 and the sample size was garnered using the Taro Yamane formula.

Yamane Formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Statement of Problem 1: The researchers used the percentage formula to identify the respondents' academic performance.

$$P = f/N \times 100\%$$

Where:

P is the percentage, f is the frequency, and N is the number of respondents.

Statement of Problems 2 and 3: The researchers employed the weighted mean formula to gauge the student's motivation level and their perception of their teachers' feedback abilities.

Formula:

$$\text{Weighted Mean} = \frac{\sum x}{N}$$

Where;

x = level of preference

N = the no. of learners

$$\text{Weighted Mean} = \frac{fx_1 + fx_2 + \dots + fx_n}{f_1 + f_2 + \dots + f_n}$$

Where;

X = level of preference

F = the frequency

Statement of Problems 4, 5, and 6: The researchers used the Pearson's R correlational coefficient to measure the linear association between students' motivation and academic performance, between teachers' feedback skills and students' academic performance, and between teachers' feedback skills and students' motivation. It will determine if there is or no significant relationship using this formula.

Formula:

Where;

- r = Pearson Coefficient
- n = number of pairs of stock
- $\sum xy$ = sum of products of the paired stocks
- $\sum x$ = sum of the x scores
- $\sum y$ = sum of the y scores
- $\sum x^2$ = sum of the squared x scores
- $\sum y^2$ = sum of the squared y scores

Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

1. Academic Performance

In terms of academic performance, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the **Academic Performance** of the Respondents.

Table 1
Academic Performance

Academic Performance	Frequency	Percentage
75-79%	2	1.3
80-84%	33	22.2
85-89%	68	45.7
90% and above	46	30.8
TOTAL	149	100

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents. The data shows that for academic performance, which gets **85-89%**, **68** responded with a percentage of **45.7%**. For **90% and above**, **46** responded with a percentage of **30.8%**, **80-84%**, **33** responded with a percentage of **22.2%**, and lastly, **75-79%**, **2** responded with a percentage of **1.3%**. All in All, **149** respondents answered the questionnaire. The result reveals that most of the respondents got **85-89%** on their academic performance, and

the researchers interpreted that most of the respondents were outstanding, very satisfactory, and satisfactory in their academic performance Based on DepEd.

The result of these findings is related to the theory of academic performance (Top) by Elger (2007); the top refers to the capacity to make a good result and performer as a person, while the level of performance represents a student's educational journey. According to Elger, the theory of performance is a challenging factor in improving academic performance through empowering students to help them learn and grow.

In relation to the findings, most of the respondents have a GWA of 85-89%, which indicates that they are performing well in their academic performance. This may suggest that the type of teaching and learning strategies used by teachers are effectively implemented to improve their academic performance.

According to Brew et al. (2021), Good academic performance is essential to the educational system. However, there are many factors to be considered that influence students' academic performance in senior high schools. The action of staying away from school without a good reason affects the student's academic performance because it leads to school dropouts. Also, the students who are not capable of studying because of their parent's income and the accessibility and availability of textbooks influence their ability to develop

academic performance. This study supports that the highest GWA of the selected senior high school is 85-89%, suggesting that the school and teachers provide quality education to help students learn and perform well even in many circumstances that affect the student's academic performance, teachers' make sure to meet the students' standard to learn.

2. Students' Level of Motivation

The following section presents the **Students' Level of Motivation**.

2.1 Intrinsic Motivation

In terms of intrinsic Motivation, the indicators were explored. The table below shows the **level of motivation** of the respondents in terms of intrinsic Motivation.

Table 2.1
Level of Motivation in terms of Intrinsic Motivation

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. I like to learn from different subjects.	3.61	0.52	Strongly Agree
2. I make sure to do better at any activity.	3.52	0.55	Strongly Agree
3. I felt competent after doing the performance task.	3.34	0.61	Strongly Agree
4. I find it necessary to perform well on every task in school.	3.38	0.63	Strongly Agree
5. I am teaching myself because it feels good to learn.	3.48	0.61	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.47	0.58	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 - Agree, 2.49-1.75 - Disagree, 1.74-1.00 - Strongly Disagree

Table 2.1 presents the indicators of the level of motivation of the learners in terms of intrinsic motivation. Based on the result, Respondents do Strongly Agree, the respondents like *to learn from different subjects*, which obtained the highest mean of **3.61** and a standard deviation of **0.52**, *make sure to do better at any activity*, with a mean of **3.52** and standard deviation of **0.55**, the respondents *like to teach themselves because it feels good to learn*, with a mean of **3.48** and standard deviation of **0.61**. Additionally, the respondents also *found it necessary to perform well on every task in school*, with a mean of **3.38** and a standard deviation of **0.63** and *felt competent after doing a performance task* with a mean of **3.34** and a standard deviation of **0.61**. Overall, based on the result of Table 2.1, most of the respondents are intrinsically motivated, and students can benefit from it, such as increasing the students' intrinsic motivation and academic performance in terms of learning from a different subject, making sure to do better at any activity, teaching themselves because the respondents feel good when learning. Also, the respondents find it necessary to perform well on every task in school and feel competent after doing the performance task. These indicators show that the respondents are performing well in school and find satisfaction in improving their academic performance.

According to Santos (2019), students' intrinsic motivations are primarily driven by the student's interest and curiosity, which can sustain the students' passion, creativity, and learning efforts despite external rewards. Also, the findings of Zaccone and Pedrini (2019) Support the results of the study presented in Table 2.1, which suggests that Intrinsic motivation contributes to the learning of the students. It influences the learners to learn more effectively, and the students use it to acquire more knowledge. It concludes that educational settings should spend more effort to increase the student's intrinsic motivation to achieve higher learning effectiveness.

2.2 Extrinsic Motivation

In terms of Extrinsic Motivation, the indicators were explored. The table 2.2 indicates the **level of Motivation** of the respondents in terms of Extrinsic Motivation.

Table 2.2 Presents the indicators of the level of motivation of learners in terms of extrinsic motivation. Based on the result, Respondents do Strongly Agree, the respondents are *studying to finish studies* with the highest mean of **3.67** and standard deviation of **0.57** and *improve the academic performance to achieve higher grades* with a mean of **3.59** and standard deviation of **0.60**.

Table 2.2
Level of Motivation in terms of Extrinsic Motivation

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. I am studying to finish my studies.	3.67	0.57	Strongly Agree
2. I study to avoid consequences from my parents and teachers.	3.39	0.62	Strongly Agree
3. I am doing my homework because all the tasks are graded.	3.59	0.62	Strongly Agree
4. I improve my academic performance to achieve higher grades.	3.59	0.60	Strongly Agree
5. I work hard on my schoolwork to receive praise from teachers.	3.35	0.69	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.52	0.62	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 – Agree, 2.49-1.75 – Disagree, 1.74-1.00 – Strongly Disagree

*The respondents are doing homework because all the tasks are graded with a mean of **3.59** and a standard deviation of **0.62**. The respondents' study to avoid consequences from parents and teachers, with a mean of **3.39** and standard deviation of **0.62** and work hard on the schoolwork to receive praise from teachers, with a mean of **3.35** and standard deviation of **0.69**.*

Overall, based on the result of Table 2.2, it seen that most of the respondents are extrinsically motivated to accomplish their desires in terms of studying to finish studies, improving academic performance to achieve higher grades, doing homework because all the tasks are graded, studying to avoid consequences from parents and teachers, and working hard to the schoolwork

to receive praise from teachers. This finding is consistent with the study conducted by Research Key (2021), which study revealed that extrinsic motivation has a significant effect on students' academic achievement.

According to Research Key (2021), students are learning by the desire to meet the expectations of others like parents and teachers or the desire to achieve the desired grades or higher grades; it involves punishment and rewards, and students use extrinsic motivation to accomplish a task that pushes themselves to achieve something it makes them to be driven in the desire to perform better in academic performance. Extrinsic Motivation plays an important role in motivating students extrinsically to meet their own expectations. It is shown that students perform well in and become more participative in class because of praises, gifts, and rewards.

2.3 Fear Motivation

In terms of Fear Motivation, the indicators were explored. The table 2.3 shows the **level of motivation** of the respondents in terms of Fear Motivation.

Table 2.3
Level of Motivation in terms of Fear Motivation

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. I pay close attention in class and participate actively to avoid negative feedback.	3.41	0.60	Strongly Agree
2. I work hard in my studies to avoid low grades.	3.53	0.56	Strongly Agree
3. I sometimes focus on what is wrong and what I could do wrong.	3.26	0.64	Strongly Agree
4. Failure plays in shaping my aspirations to learn something.	3.38	0.64	Strongly Agree
5. My desires drove me because I did not want to be embarrassed.	3.32	0.66	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.38	0.62	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 – Agree, 2.49-1.75 – Disagree, 1.74-1.00 – Strongly Disagree

Table 2.3 presents the indicators of the level of motivation of the learners in terms of fear motivation. Based on the result, the respondents Strongly Agree, the respondents *are working hard in the studies to avoid low grades*, with the highest mean of **3.53** and standard deviation of **0.56**. The respondents *pay close attention in class and participate actively to avoid negative comments*, with a mean of **3.41** and a standard deviation of **0.60**. *Failure plays a role in shaping aspirations to learn something*, with a mean of **3.38** and a standard deviation of **0.64**. Additionally, *the respondents are driven by their desires because the*

respondents do not want to be embarrassed with a mean of 3.32 and standard deviation of 0.66. The respondents are sometimes focused on what is wrong and what could do wrong, with a mean of 3.26 and a standard deviation of 0.64.

Overall, based on the result of Table 2.3, it is seen that most of the respondents strongly agree that fear is a motivator to avoid failure and embarrassment in the classroom in terms of working hard in studies to avoid low grades, paying close attention in class and participate actively to avoid negative comments. Also, failure plays in shaping aspirations to learn something, driven by the desires because the respondents do not want to be embarrassed, and focused on what is wrong and what could go wrong.

The latest study by Thomas (2014) reveals that fear can act as a motivator, which suggests that fear can move away students from their comfort zone. Students' behavior might expect fear to avoid consequences or risk; the result found that students may experience a short-term motivation that can help the students perform well in academic performance; once the students are afraid of doing something, it will help to think critically about the possible outcomes that can contribute to success.

According to Naklha (2019), they were comprehensively examining the link between the aspects of academics. This brought out fear of failing as a significant factor that influences both motivation and engagement and specified

the pitfalls associated with such fear of failure of the student based on how they are affected by fear of failure and how their motivation levels are affected.

2.4 Social Motivation

In terms of Social Motivation, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the **level of Motivation** of the respondents in terms of Social Motivation.

Table 2.4
Level of Motivation in terms of Social Motivation

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. I was able to share my knowledge with my classmates.	3.46	0.64	Strongly Agree
2. I increased communication with my fellow students in helping myself more throughout the subject.	3.46	0.60	Strongly Agree
3. I make sure to express my emotions without offending others.	3.42	0.64	Strongly Agree
4. I ask my classmates about topics that I need to learn more about.	3.50	0.63	Strongly Agree
5. I like interacting socially with knowledgeable people.	3.43	0.64	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.45	0.63	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 – Agree, 2.49-1.75 – Disagree, 1.74-1.00 – Strongly Disagree

Table 2.4 presents the indicators of the level of motivation of the learners in terms of social motivation. Based on the result, The respondents Strongly Agree, the respondents *ask classmates about topics that the respondents know*

very little about, with the highest mean of **3.50** with a standard deviation of **0.63**. Also, *sharing knowledge with classmates*, with a mean of **3.46** and standard deviation of **0.64**, and *increasing communication with fellow students in helping the respondents more throughout the subject*, with a mean of **3.46** and standard deviation of **0.60**. Moreover, *the respondents like interacting socially with knowledgeable people*, with a mean of **3.43** and a standard deviation of **0.64**, and *making sure to express emotions without offending others*, with a mean of **3.42** and a standard deviation of **0.64**.

Overall, based on the result of Table 2.4, it is seen that most of the respondents are socially motivated in socializing and collaborating with classmates in terms of asking classmates about topics that the respondents know very little about, sharing knowledge with classmates, increasing communication with fellow students in helping the respondents more throughout the subject, also interacting with knowledgeable people, and expressing emotions without offending others.

According to The International School of Thrissur (2024), socialization is crucial for personal and professional growth in students, as it enhances empathy, problem-solving, and communication skills. Exposure to diverse cultures fosters respect and appreciation for others. Socialization also aids in developing communication skills, including self-observation, comprehension,

and expression. Also, according to Safra et al. (2020), to develop cooperation and collaboration, socializing is important; building trust and impressions helps people to have a successful interaction that creates a social environment. Most of the students have a trustworthy partner who is more cooperative than others, but some are just socializing to get a benefit. Safra et al. (2020) found that social motivation involves students finding experience and interaction to develop and maintain social bonds.

3. Students' Evaluation of the Teacher' Feedback Skills

The following section presents the **Students' Evaluation of the Teachers' Feedback Skills**.

3.1 Constructive Feedback

In terms of Constructive Feedback, the indicators were explored. The table 3.1 indicates the **Students' Evaluation of the Teachers' Feedback Skills** of the respondents in terms of Constructive Feedback.

Table 3.1
Students' Evaluation of the Teachers' Feedback Skills in terms of Constructive Feedback

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. My teacher makes sure that I know what I need to do to improve.	3.60	0.56	Strongly Agree
2. My teacher has insightful feedback when I am done with my performance task.	3.50	0.63	Strongly Agree
3. My teacher ensures privacy regarding negative behaviors.	3.46	0.66	Strongly Agree
4. My teacher focuses on my performance and not on my personality.	3.37	0.71	Strongly Agree
5. My teachers are calm when giving feedback.	3.63	0.52	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.51	0.62	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 – Agree, 2.49-1.75 – Disagree, 1.74-1.00 – Strongly Disagree

Table 3.1 presents the indicators of the student's evaluation of the teacher's feedback in terms of constructive feedback. The respondents strongly agree that *teachers are calm when giving feedback*, with the highest mean of **3.63** and standard deviation of **0.52**; *teachers makes sure that the respondents know what is need to do to improve*, with a mean of **3.60** and standard deviation of **0.56**; also *teachers have insightful feedback when after the academic performance* with a mean of **3.50** and standard deviation of **0.63**, *teachers ensures privacy regarding negative behaviors* with a mean of **3.46** and standard

deviation of **0.66**, and *teachers focuses on the academic performance and not to their personality* with a mean of **0.37** and standard deviation of **0.71**.

Overall, based on Table 3.1, it is seen that most of the students strongly agree that teachers help them to improve the academic performance by providing constructive and positive feedback, such as being calm when giving feedback, making sure that the students know what is need to improve, giving insightful feedback when after academic performance, ensuring privacy regarding the negative behaviors, and focusing on the academic performance rather than the students' personality.

Ahmed et al. (2021), research highlight the importance of teachers' constructive feedback in the teaching and learning process the students, as it motivates students to determine things that need to be improved, students enhance self-efficacy, and encourages hard work through giving constructive feedback. Additionally, according to the University of South Wales (2023), feedback is beneficial to the student's learning process when it is constructive, timely, and meaningful. It will help the students to be more engaged and encourage them to think critically about improving their academic performance; the feedback should be delivered throughout the course. These findings highlight the importance of giving constructive feedback to improve the student's academic performance.

3.2 Formal Feedback

In terms of Formal Feedback, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the **Students' Evaluation of the Teachers' Feedback Skills** of the respondents in terms of Formal Feedback.

Table 3.2
Students' Evaluation of the Teachers' Feedback Skills
in terms of Formal Feedback

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. My teachers present rubrics/criteria during the performance.	3.66	0.55	Strongly Agree
2. My teachers provide feedback in our free time.	3.58	0.58	Strongly Agree
3. My teacher assesses my performance based on what I do.	3.56	0.60	Strongly Agree
4. My teachers provide explanations for both what and why during feedback sessions.	3.62	0.57	Strongly Agree
5. My teacher gives recommendations to enhance my academic performance.	3.64	0.54	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.61	0.57	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 – Agree, 2.49-1.75 – Disagree, 1.74-1.00 – Strongly Disagree

Table 3.2 presents the indicators of the student's evaluation of the teacher's feedback in terms of formal feedback. The respondents strongly agree that *teachers provided rubrics/criteria during the performance*, with the highest mean of **3.66** and a standard deviation of **0.55**. Also, *teachers give*

recommendations to enhance students' academic performance, with a mean of **3.64** and a standard deviation of **0.54**, and *teachers provide explanations for both what and why during feedback sessions*, with a mean of **3.62** and a standard deviation of **0.57**. Moreover, the respondents also strongly agree that *teachers provide feedback when free time*, with a mean of **3.58** and a standard deviation of **0.58**, and *teacher assesses performance based on what the students' do*, with a mean of **3.56** and a standard deviation of **0.60**.

Overall, based on the result of Table 3.2, it is seen that most of the respondents strongly agree that teachers assess and provide feedback that will help to address strengths and weaknesses for further improvement, such as providing rubrics/criteria during the performance, giving recommendations to enhance the academic performance, providing explanation for both what and why during the feedback sessions, providing feedback during free time, and assessing their performance based on what the students' do.

According to Schooley (2023), formal feedback is used to address the student's strengths and weaknesses and identify the ways to improve the student's academic performance; a teacher can help the students grow, and one way to do it is to have an open, and honest communication to the students. Students should feel comfortable when communicating with the teacher about their performance. The result found that formal feedback is excellent for tracking

the student's performance and ensuring that the students are aware if the teacher is satisfied with their performance.

Additionally, the formal feedback, which is well-planned and structured, is more helpful in highlighting the students' progress. This method promotes a comfortable foundation for information sharing and provides space for feedback exchange between the students and the teacher.

3.3 Informal Feedback

In terms of Informal Feedback, the indicators were explored. The table 3.3 indicates the **Students' Evaluation of the Teachers' Feedback Skills** of the respondents in terms of Informal Feedback.

Table 3.3 presents the indicators of the student's evaluation of the teacher's feedback in terms of Informal feedback. The respondents strongly agree that *teacher provides positive feedback when the task is completed correctly*, with the highest mean of **3.56** and standard deviation of **0.61**; *teacher provides feedback, praising collaborative efforts and offering suggestions to students' teamwork skills*, with a mean of **3.54** and standard deviation of **0.62**. Also, *teachers take a moment to acknowledge students' dedication to studying and give suggestions on how can improve*, with a mean of **3.51** and a standard deviation of **0.63**.

Table 3.3
Students' Evaluation of the Teachers' Feedback Skills
in terms of Informal Feedback

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. My teachers provide positive feedback when I complete the task correctly.	3.56	0.61	Strongly Agree
2. My teacher leaves personalized notes on my tasks, acknowledging my efforts.	3.40	0.61	Strongly Agree
3. My teachers take a moment to acknowledge my dedication to studying and give suggestions on how I can improve.	3.51	0.63	Strongly Agree
4. My teachers tell my parents about how I perform in the class.	3.40	0.69	Strongly Agree
5. My teacher provides feedback, praising collaborative efforts and offering suggestions for our teamwork skills.	3.54	0.62	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.48	0.63	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 – Agree, 2.49-1.75 – Disagree, 1.74-1.00 – Strongly Disagree

Moreover, the respondents also strongly agree that *teacher tells parents about how the students perform in class*, with a mean of **3.40** and standard deviation of **0.69**, and *teacher leaves a personalized note on students' tasks acknowledging efforts*, with a mean of **3.40** and a standard deviation of **0.61**.

Overall, based on the result of Table 3.3, it is seen that most of the respondents strongly agree that their teachers acknowledge the efforts of the students and provide suggestions for improvement, such as providing positive

feedback when students complete the task correctly, providing feedback, praising collaborative efforts, and offering suggestions about the students' teamwork skills, acknowledging their dedication in studying and give suggestion on how the students will improve, also telling parents about how students' perform in class, and leaving personalized note on task acknowledging the efforts of students.

According to the Victoria University of Wellington (2013), Informal feedback is delivered as an alternative method. It has many advantages, such as being used to obtain quick and easy information, providing timely constructive information to assist the students learning, and the information being collected anytime. Providing appropriate feedback can identify short or long-term and unable changes; it Indicates where clarification is needed. Informal feedback informs the learning process and encourages active student reflection.

3.4 Corrective Feedback

In terms of Corrective Feedback, the indicators were explored. The table 3.4 indicates the **Students' Evaluation of the Teachers' Feedback Skills** of the respondents in terms of Corrective Feedback.

Table 3.4
Students' Evaluation of the Teachers' Feedback Skills in terms of
Corrective Feedback

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. My teachers identify the errors in my work, ensuring that I understand what needs correction.	3.58	0.57	Strongly Agree
2. My teachers provide clear examples of how I improve.	3.54	0.60	Strongly Agree
3. My teachers pointed out the areas where I showed effort and where I did well.	3.56	0.57	Strongly Agree
4. My teacher offers a detailed explanation of the correct solution or approach when he/she identifies the error.	3.54	0.64	Strongly Agree
5. My teachers provide feedback on all the mistakes in my written work.	3.54	0.66	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.55	0.61	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 – Agree, 2.49-1.75 – Disagree, 1.74-1.00 – Strongly Disagree

Table 3.4 presents the indicators of the student's evaluation of the teachers' feedback in terms of Corrective feedback. The respondents strongly agree that *teachers identified the error in work, ensuring that students understand what needs correction* with the highest mean of **3.58** and standard deviation of **0.57**; also, *teachers pointed out the areas where students showed*

effort and where students did well with a mean of **3.56** and standard deviation of **0.57**, and *teachers provide feedback on all the mistakes in written work* with a mean of **3.54** and standard deviation of **0.66**. Moreover, the respondents also strongly agree that *teachers offer a detailed explanation of the correct solution or approach when he/she identifies the errors* with a mean of **3.54** and standard deviation of **0.64**, and *teachers provides clear examples of how students will improve* with a mean of **3.54** and standard deviation of **0.60**.

Overall, based on the result of Table 3.4, it is seen that most of the respondents strongly agree that teachers correct errors and explain where the students go wrong and what the students need to improve, such as identifying the error in their work, ensuring that students understand what needs correction, pointing out the areas where students showed effort and where students did well, providing feedback on all the mistakes in written works, offering a detailed explanation of the correct solution or approach when the teacher identifies the errors, and proving clear examples of how the students will improve. This finding is consistent with the study of Guinness, K. et al. (2020) Overview of corrective feedback.

According to Dela Cruz and Wong (2022), on the contrary, the vital part that feedback plays in the development of student's critical thinking capabilities, even though students may like oral or written feedback and whether the

feedback is negative or positive. The advice given by the instructor plays an important role when students struggle with some tasks; it helps to improve their self-evaluation skills, which heavily influence their academic results. Students may strengthen their problem-solving ability, reinforce their concept comprehension, and increase their chances of getting more positive results.

According to Guinness et al. (2020), students can make mistakes or errors as they learn new skills in their learning; corrective feedback is critical to the learning process and provides additional information on whether the students' answers are correct. Corrective feedback simply supplies students with correct answers and explains why their answers are correct or incorrect. Teachers should require the students to respond actively to repeat the correct answer in corrective feedback. The result found that corrective feedback is a powerful tool to address errors and to meet the expectations of teachers regarding the student's academic performance.

4. Significant relationship between students' motivation and academic performance.

The researchers determined the significant relationship between the student's motivation and academic performance of the selected senior high school students. The significant Relationship was determined using the **Pearson R correlational coefficient**.

Table 4 shows the results of the conducted survey.

Table 4
Significant Relationship Between Students' Motivation
and Academic Performance.

Variable	r value	p-value	Decision (H ₀)	Interpretation
Students' Motivation and Academic Performance	0.206	0.012	Reject H ₀	Significant (<i>Weak Positive Correlation</i>)

p<0.05= Significant, p>0.05=Not significant

Table 4 presents the relationship between the Students' Motivation and the Academic performance of the learners. In terms of the Students' Motivation and Academic performance, with an R-value of **0.206** or a P-value of **0.012**; thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between Students' Motivation and the Academic Performance of the learners.

Based on the interpretation, it has a Weak Positive Correlation because not all the students have the same motivation to use in their academic performance; some students are intrinsically motivated because of personal satisfaction, some are extrinsically motivated because of the reward and praise, some are uses fear as a motivator because of failure, and some students are socially motivated, every student have different kinds of motivator that pushes their ability.

Using the **Pearson R Correlation** came up with the result that can be seen in Table 4. The table shows that the relationship between Students' Motivation and the Academic performance of the learners has a significant relationship. The researchers also concluded that in terms of Students' Motivation, there is such thing to do with the academic performance of the selected senior high school students, so it has a significant relationship.

According to Liu et al. (2022), the correlation between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and academic performance across different age groups, such as elementary school to college students, is crucial for understanding the factors that influence students' success. Elements between motivation and academic achievement provide how various motivations influence student outcomes and academic performance. The result found that the intrinsic motivation of students helps them to perform better academically compared to the students who use extrinsic motivation.

5. Significant relationship between teachers' feedback skills and students' academic performance.

The researchers determined the significant relationship between the teachers' feedback skills and the academic performance of the selected senior high school students. The significant Relationship was determined using the **Pearson R correlational coefficient**.

Table 5 Shows the result of the conducted survey.

Table 5
Significant relationship between teachers' feedback skills and students' academic performance.

Variable	r value	p-value	Decision (H ₀)	Interpretation
Teachers' Feedback Skills and Students' Academic Performance	0.194	0.018	Reject H ₀	Significant (<i>Very Weak Positive Correlation</i>)

p < 0.05 = Significant, p > 0.05 = Not significant

Table 5 presents the relationship between the Teachers' Feedback Skills and Students' Academic Performance. In terms of the Teachers' Feedback Skills and Students' Academic Performance, the R-Value of **0.194** or the P-Value of **0.018**, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between Students' Motivation and the Academic Performance of the learners.

Based on the interpretation, it has a Very Weak Positive Correlation because not all the students have the same way on how they will accept the Teachers' Feedback; students have different approaches or preferences on how well they perceive feedback, and some students take the teacher's feedback as a compliment that they do well in class or academic performance. However, it needs to improve or develop, but some students are not taking the feedback seriously and do not think that that feedback can help to improve the student's academic performance.

Using the **Pearson R Correlation** came up with the result that can be seen in Table 5. The table shows that in the relationship between Teachers' Feedback Skills and Students' Academic Performance, have a significant relationship. The researchers also concluded that in terms of Teachers' Feedback Skills, there is such thing to do with the academic performance of the selected senior high school students, so it has a significant relationship.

According to Maharma and Abusa'aleek (2022), the feedback given to the students plays a vital role in academic performance. Thus, it is also essential for teachers to analyze what feedback should be given to the students. Also, students must analyze the teacher's feedback to apply the feedback to academic performance easily. The result discovered that accurate and detailed feedback of teachers to the students reduces the discouragement.

According to Selveraj and Wahi (2021), teacher feedback affects students' academic performance; it helps to determine the student's strengths and improve students' weaknesses. It uses a systematic literature review to explore the connection between students' academic performance and teachers' feedback. The analysis reveals that while feedback helps students improve academically, also feedback in written form can negatively influence the learning of students. The paper emphasizes the need for teachers to provide self-improvement feedback for students.

6. Significant relationship between teachers' feedback skills and students' motivation.

The researchers determined the significant relationship between the teachers' feedback skills and students' motivation and of the selected senior high school students. The significant Relationship was determined using the **Pearson R correlational coefficient**.

Table 6 shows the results of the conducted survey.

Table 6
Significant Relationship Between Teachers' Feedback Skills
and Students' Motivation

Variable	r value	p-value	Decision (H ₀)	Interpretation
Teachers' Feedback Skills and Students' Motivation	0.750	< 0.01	Reject H ₀	Significant (<i>Strong Positive Correlation</i>)

p<0.05= Significant, p>0.05=Not significant

Table 5 presents the relationship between the Teachers' Feedback Skills and Students' Motivation. In terms of the Teachers' Feedback Skills and Students' Motivation, with an R-value of **0.750** or P-Value of **<0.01**, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between Teachers' Feedback Skills and Students' Motivation.

Based on the interpretation, it has a Strong Positive Correlation, which means that the students are motivated when they receive feedback from their teachers because it shows that their teachers gave value to how they perform in class, and it motivates them to perform well.

Using the **Pearson R Correlation**, come up with the result as can be seen in Table 6. The table shows that the relationship between Teachers' Feedback Skills and Students' Motivation has a significant relationship. The researchers also concluded that in terms of Teachers' Feedback Skills, there is such thing to do with the Students' Motivation of the selected senior high school students, so it has a significant relationship. According to Johnson (2017), teachers motivate the students to learn by providing positive feedback to encourage and develop the students' academic performance. Providing feedback helps the students to believe in their abilities and control their own learning. Many factors motivate the students to learn, it can be intrinsic or extrinsic. On the other hand, motivated students learn naturally by interest and enjoyment and to the rewards that a student can get after getting the outcomes.

Additionally, the role of the teacher in supporting students' learning and creating conditions for motivation is impossible to underestimate. While students have inborn learning capabilities, the external factor, such as a teacher, is required when students lose their interest. Such teachers can help to bring back motivation through autonomy, relevance, relatedness, competence, passion, and self-efficacy in the subject of teaching. Overall, these lead to increasing both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, which creates a positive learning process and environment.

7. Based on the Study, what action plan can be proposed to support the teachers' feedback skills and students' motivation?

Improving Teachers' Feedbacking Skills to Provide Effective Feedback for Students

Key Areas	Goals/Objectives	Activities/Strategies	Person Involve	Time Frame	Resources Needed	Success Indicators
Teachers' Feedbacking Skills	To improve the skills of teachers in providing effective feedback that supports the students learning.	Workshop for teachers to enhance their skills on providing feedback.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers • Students • School admin • School 	Year Round	Technology Materials Facilitators	80% will increase their ability to provide effective feedback
	To help teachers focus on students' outcomes.	Survey to gather feedback from students about teacher feedback they received and experiences.		Year Round	Evaluation/Survey Tools	90% the effectiveness of teacher feedback practices from the student to enhance the feedback to meet students' needs.
	To allow teachers understand different feedback styles and incorporate feedback as a student's motivation.	Reflection Journals for teachers to document their feedback practices, challenges, and success, promoting self-awareness and growth.		Year Round	Journals	85% that the teachers will understand the different feedback styles and use it as a motivation for students.

Enhancing Students Motivation

Key Areas	Goals/Objectives	Activities/Strategies	Person Involve	Time Frame	Resources Needed	Success Indicators
Students ' Motivation	To increase students' motivation to improve academically	Workshop to help students set an achievable academic goal.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School • Administrator • Teacher • Students • Parents 	Year Round	Facilitators Technology Materials Teambuilding activities	80% of students continued to actively pursue their academic goals and apply the strategies learned
	To foster students' engagement in the learning process	Implement recognition program to celebrate students' progress and academic achievement.		Year Round	Certificates Parents involvement	80% effectiveness to motivate the students in their overall academic success.
	To contribute to students' long-term academic and personal growth	Offer extracurricular activities targeting students' interests, participation in arts or sports program		Year Round	Facilities Sports and arts equipment	90% increased student retention and engagement in school.
	To support students' academic progress to be motivated	Meeting between parents and teachers in providing guidance on how they can support their child's learning		Year Round	Parents Support	90% parents understanding and supporting their child's academic progress

Conclusions

The findings of the study provide insights into the feedback skills of teachers for students, the level of academic performance, and the level of motivation of the learners. Most of the learners who participated in the study demonstrated teachers' feedback skills as an important aspect of their learning; it indicates that teachers' feedback contributes to their motivation and helps improve their academic performance. In examining the relationship between students' motivation and academic performance, the study found a significant correlation. There is a significant relationship between students' motivation and students' academic performance, but it has a weak positive correlation because of the learner's motivation differences.

In determining the relationship between teachers' feedback skills and students' academic performance, there is a relationship between teachers' feedback skills and students' academic performance, but it has a very weak positive correlation because students have different preferences on how they will perceive the feedback. Lastly, in examining the relationship between teachers' feedback skills and students' motivation, the study found a significant correlation and revealed that teachers' feedback motivates students to perform well in school. These two have a strong positive correlation; when a teacher provides feedback, it reinforces the students' strengths, which improves the learner's confidence and motivation to learn.

In conclusion, this study provides a clear understanding of students' evaluation of teachers' feedback skills, students' level of motivation, students' level of academic performance, and the significant relationship between these three variables. This finding suggests that teachers' feedback contributes to the student's motivation and improving their academic performance. Further research can further explore the different factors that affect the teachers in giving feedback.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, several recommendations can be made to effectively deliver and enhance the way of giving feedback to the students. Administrators should foster a school culture where feedback is valued and seen as an essential tool for student growth and motivation. Collaborate with teachers, students, parents, and other stakeholders to gather input and feedback on existing practices and to co-create strategies for enhancing feedback and student motivation in the school environment.

Teachers should employ a variety of feedback methods, including verbal, written, and peer feedback, tailored to individual student needs and learning styles. Provide feedback promptly after student performance to maintain relevance and effectiveness in promoting motivation. Also, teachers should engage students in a supportive and positive learning environment where

students feel valued, respected, and motivated to engage with feedback and improve their performance.

Pre-service instructors, those training to become teachers, should receive education on the advantages and limitations of teachers' feedback skills, student's motivation, and academic performance. They should be equipped with the knowledge and skills to incorporate this study into their teaching practice effectively. Additionally, they should be trained in assessing the effectiveness of these studies in enhancing students' academic performance, allowing for ongoing improvement and adaptation.

Learners should communicate their preferences regarding feedback to teachers, including the format, frequency, and level of detail that they find most helpful and motivating. To actively engage with feedback provided by teachers, reflecting on strengths in areas for improvement, learners must set personal learning goals based on feedback received from teachers, seek clarification from teachers when feedback is unclear, and use feedback as a tool for self-assessment to identify strategies for improvement.

Parents Should collaborate and communicate with teachers, sharing information about their child's preferences and learning needs to facilitate a collaborative and supportive learning environment.

Future researchers can expand the findings of this study by getting the learners' demographic profile. They can delve deeper into understanding how this study can be combined to enhance students' academic performance further. Furthermore, research can be conducted in different educational contexts, such as online and blended learning environments, to investigate the teacher's feedback skills, students' motivation, and academic performance.

By following these recommendations, educational institutions can effectively integrate teachers' feedback skills, student's motivation, and academic performance into their teaching practices, promoting students' academic success and development. Ongoing research and collaboration among educators, administrators, and parents will further contribute to the advancement and refinement of these studies.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: Letter of Validation, Validation Sheet, and Revisions

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
PROVINCE OF BATANGAS
CITY GOVERNMENT OF TANAUAN
TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

January 24, 2024

VENICE S. PAGASPAS, LPT, MAED
Teacher III
Tanauan City Integrated High School

Madam:

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled **"Teachers' Feedbacking Skills, Students' Motivation, and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students"**.

In this regard, we are seeking your expertise in helping us validate the Self-Made questionnaire that we will use to measure the variables needed in the study. Attached here is a copy of the questionnaire that we wish to employ in the said study. Your comments and suggestions will be highly appreciated and will be a great help to this undertaking.

We are hoping for your favorable response and wholehearted consideration regarding this matter.

Thank you so much and more power.

Very truly yours,

John Erick M. Pamplona

Kenneth M. Seda

Larissa R. Gonzales

Lenje R. Pajarillo

Lorenz U. Verola
Researchers

Noted:

MR. ROJANE F. BERNAS
Thesis Adviser

Approved/Remarks:

VENICE S. PAGASPAS, LPT, MAED
Teacher III

Questionnaire Validation Sheet

Name of Validator : Venice S. Pagaspas
 Highest Educational Qualification : PhDE-English (CAR)
 Position Held : Teacher III
 Field of Specialization : English
 Signature : (Mez)

Directions:

A. Refer to the attached research instrument for validation.

B. Please use the Rating scale below and encircle the number that corresponds to the evaluation of each value item.

4	-	very valid	2	-	less valid
3	-	moderately valid	1	-	need for revalidation

I. Level of Academic Performance

A. General Weighted Average

Value item	I.A.1	1	2	3	4
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II. Level of Students Motivation

A. Intrinsic Motivation

Value item	II.A.1	1	2	3	④
	II.A.2	1	2	3	④
	II.A.3	1	2	3	④
	II.A.4	1	2	③	4
	II.A.5	1	2	3	④

B. Extrinsic Motivation

Value item	II.B.1	1	②	3	4
	II.B.2	1	2	③	4

	II.B.3	1	2	3	4
	II.B.4	1	2	3	4
	II.B.5	1	2	3	4
C. Social Motivation					
Value Item	II.C.1	1	2	3	4
	II.C.2	1	2	3	4
	II.C.3	1	2	3	4
	II.C.4	1	2	3	4
	II.C.5	1	2	3	4
D. Fear Motivation					
Value Item	II.D.1	1	2	3	4
	II.D.2	1	2	3	4
	II.D.3	1	2	3	4
	II.D.4	1	2	3	4
	II.D.5	1	2	3	4

III. Students evaluation of teachers feedbacking skills

A. Constructive Feedback

Value Item	III.A.1	1	2	3	4
	III.A.2	1	2	3	4
	III.A.3	1	2	3	4
	III.A.4	1	2	3	4
	III.A.5	1	2	3	4

B. Formal Feedback

Value Item	III.B.1	1	2	3	4
	III.B.2	1	2	3	4
	III.B.3	1	2	3	4
	III.B.4	1	2	3	4
	III.B.5	1	2	3	4

C. Informal Feedback

Value item

III.C.1	1	2	3	4
III.C.2	1	2	3	4
III.C.3	1	2	3	4
III.C.4	1	2	3	4
III.C.5	1	2	3	4

D. Corrective Feedback

Value item

III.D.1	1	2	3	4
III.D.2	1	2	3	4
III.D.3	1	2	3	4
III.D.4	1	2	3	4
III.D.5	1	2	3	4

Remarks/Recommendation

- Follow correct format in constructing an instrument.
- Be specific in constructing each indicator.
- Be mindful of the correct grammar.
- Make sure that all the indicators are PARALLEL in terms of word/sentence constructions.
- Put translation in (Filipino)

Overall Rating

Please check (✓) appropriate rating.

- Approved to be used as presented
- Approved to be used with revisions as indicated
- Disapproved, the researchers must make another questionnaire

title _____

Name: _____ (Optional)
 Directions: _____

Age: _____

1. What is your General weighted average? _____
 I - Level of Motivation of the Student

	Strongly Agree (4) Justify	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
Intrinsic Motivation:				
✓ 1. I enjoy my subject in school.				
2. I am pretty good and skilled at any activity.				
✓ 3. After doing the performance task, I felt quite competent.				
4. It is important to me to do well in <u>at</u> each task in school.				
✓ 5. I am teaching myself something because it feels good to learn.				
Extrinsic Motivation:				
1. I study to graduate.				
2. I study to avoid punishments from my parents <u>or</u> teachers.				
✓ 3. I complete my homework because the teacher <u>gives us marks for</u> each assignment.				
4. I am doing my academic performance better to have higher grades.				
5. I make my academic performance great to receive <u>a</u> praise <u>for</u> teachers.				
Social Motivation:				
✓ 1. I was able to share learning experiences with other students.				
2. <u>Inclusive</u> increased <u>work</u> contact with fellow students <u>helped me</u> more throughout the subject.				
✓ 3. It is important to me to be able to express my feelings without offending others.				
✓ 4. It is important to me to spend time with people who know about the topics that I know very little about.				
✓ 5. It is important to me to socialized <u>with</u> knowledgeable <u>persons</u> : <u>people</u> .				
Fear Motivation:				
1. It gives me motivation to work harder and learn the topics more thoroughly. ?				
2. Fear makes me scared of failing. Refrain				
✓ 3. I sometimes focus on what is wrong and what I could go wrong.				
4. Fear plays in shaping my aspirations and motivates me to learn something new. Refrain				

Students' Evaluation of the Teachers' Feedback

II

✓ 5. I was driven by my desires to be as effective as possible and to do better in my academic performance.				
Constructive Feedback:	Strong			
1. My teachers feedback is provided effectively.				
2. My teachers feedback is timely and prompt.				
3. My teachers feedback is clear and easy to understand.				
4. My teachers feedback is relevant and meaningful.				
5. My teachers feedback is constructive and encouraging.				
Formal Feedback:				
1. I prefer to receive teacher feedback when it is One-on-one.				
✓ 2. My teacher gives a lot of notice about my performance.				
✓ 3. When my teacher is providing feedback privately, my teacher makes sure that time is convenient for both of us.				
4. My teacher formal feedback engages my critical-thinking skills.				
5. My teacher feedback is scheduled and structured.				
Informal Feedback:				
1. I appreciate the teacher feedback when my teacher says "Good Job".				
2. My teacher feedback is spontaneous and unprompted.				
3. My teacher offers as a quick response to my actions.				
4. My teacher gives specific feedback that explains what and why.				
5. My teacher provides suggestions for my improvement.				
Corrective Feedback:				
1. My teacher feedback is specific about my work.				
✓ 2. My teacher offers clear examples of how I improve.				
✓ 3. My teachers point out the areas where I showed effort and where I did well.				
4. I prefer written feedback than oral feedback.				
5. For each mistake I make, my teachers provide examples.				

Constructive

Formal

Informal

parallel

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
 PROVINCE OF BATANGAS
CITY GOVERNMENT OF TANAUAN
 TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

January 24, 2024

CHRISTIAN D. TEJERESAS, LPT
 Master Teacher I
 Tanauan City Integrated High School

Sir:

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled "**Teachers' Feedbacking Skills, Students' Motivation, and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students**".

In this regard, we are seeking your expertise in helping us validate the Self-Made questionnaire that we will use to measure the variables needed in the study. Attached here with is a copy of the questionnaire that we wish to employ in the said study. Your comments and suggestions will be highly appreciated and will be a great help to this undertaking.

We are hoping for your favorable response and wholehearted consideration regarding this matter.

Thank you so much and more power.

Very truly yours,

[Signature]
John Erick M. Pamplona

[Signature]
Kenneth M. Seda

[Signature]
Larina R. Gonzales

[Signature]
Lennie R. Pararillo

[Signature]
Lorenz U. Verola
 Researchers

Noted:

[Signature]
MR. ROJANE F. BERNAS
 Thesis Adviser

Approved/Remarks:

[Signature]
CHRISTIAN D. TEJERESAS, LPT
 Master Teacher I

Questionnaire Validation Sheet

Name of Validator : CHRISTIAN D. TEJERITA
 Highest Educational Qualification : MAEd GC
 Position Held : MT
 Field of Specialization : Psychology
 Signature : [Signature] 1/25/24

Directions:

A. Refer to the attached research instrument for validation.

B. Please use the Rating scale below and encircle the number that corresponds to the evaluation of each value item.

4	-	very valid	2	-	less valid
3	-	moderately valid	1	-	need for revalidation

I. Level of Academic Performance

A. General Weighted Average

Value item	I.A.1	1	2	3	④
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II. Level of Students Motivation

A. Intrinsic Motivation

Value item	II.A.1	1	2	3	④
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	II.A.2	1	2	3	④
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	II.A.3	1	2	3	④
--	--------	---	---	---	---

	II.A.4	1	2	3	④
--	--------	---	---	---	---

	II.A.5	1	2	3	④
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B. Extrinsic Motivation

Value item	II.B.1	1	2	3	④
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	II.B.2	1	2	3	④
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	II.B.3	1	2	3	4
	II.B.4	1	2	3	4
	II.B.5	1	2	3	4
C. Fear Motivation					
Value Item	II.C.1	1	2	3	4
	II.C.2	1	2	3	4
	II.C.3	1	2	3	4
	II.C.4	1	2	3	4
	II.C.5	1	2	3	4
D. Social Motivation					
Value Item	II.D.1	1	2	3	4
	II.D.2	1	2	3	4
	II.D.3	1	2	3	4
	II.D.4	1	2	3	4
	II.D.5	1	2	3	4

III. Students evaluation of teachers feedbacking skills

A. Constructive Feedback

Value Item	III.A.1	1	2	3	4
	III.A.2	1	2	3	4
	III.A.3	1	2	3	4
	III.A.4	1	2	3	4
	III.A.5	1	2	3	4

B. Formal Feedback

Value Item	III.B.1	1	2	3	4
	III.B.2	1	2	3	4
	III.B.3	1	2	3	4
	III.B.4	1	2	3	4
	III.B.5	1	2	3	4

C. Informal Feedback

Value item

III.C.1	1	2	3	4
III.C.2	1	2	3	4
III.C.3	1	2	3	4
III.C.4	1	2	3	4
III.C.5	1	2	3	4

D. Corrective Feedback

Value item

III.D.1	1	2	3	4
III.D.2	1	2	3	4
III.D.3	1	2	3	4
III.D.4	1	2	3	4
III.D.5	1	2	3	4

Remarks/Recommendation

Overall Rating

Please check (✓) appropriate rating.

- Approved to be used as presented
- Approved to be used with revisions as indicated
- Disapproved, the researchers must make another questionnaire

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE
School of Education

Dear Respondents,

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled **“Teachers’ Feedbacking Skills, Student’s Motivation and, Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High Students”**.

We will ensure the confidentiality and consent of the respondents; the researchers will provide them with all the necessary information about the study and its objectives. Thank you and may God bless you.

The Researchers

Name: _____

Age: _____

Grade level: _____

1. What is your General Weighted Average in the First (1st) Semestral Grading? _____

Directions: The following are set of indicators that will describe your evaluation of your **teachers’ feedback skills** and the level of your **motivation** as a student. Using the 4-point scale shown below, indicate the degree of your agreement and disagreement in the following statement indicators of the variables described below. All responses that will be gathered by this research shall be treated with confidentiality.

4- Strongly Agree 3- Agree 2- Disagree 1- Strongly Disagree

I. Level of Motivation of the Students

A. Intrinsic Motivation

	4	3	2	1
1. I enjoy my subject in school.				
2. I am good and skilled at any activity.				
3. After doing the performance task, I felt competent. <i>after doing the performance task.</i>				
4. It is important to me to do well in each task in school.				
5. I am teaching myself something because it feels good to learn.				

B. Extrinsic Motivation

	4	3	2	1
1. I am studying to finish my study. <i>consequences.</i>				
2. I study to avoid punishments from my parents and teachers.				
3. I am doing my homework because my teacher gave scores for each assignment. <i>all the assignments are graded.</i>				
4. I am doing my academic performance better to have higher grades.				
5. I make my academic performance great to receive praise from teachers. <i>school tasks</i>				

C. Fear Motivation

	4	3	2	1
1. I encourage myself to pay close attention in class, <i>and</i> participate actively, and avoid distractions, to avoid negative attention. <i>so as not to be told badly.</i>				
2. Failing grades encourage me to study hard.				
3. I sometimes focus on what is wrong and what I could go wrong.				
4. Failure plays in shaping my aspirations and motivates me to learn something				

Social vs. extrinsic

rew-				
5. I was driven by my desires ^{because I don't want to be embarrassed} to be as effective as possible and to do better in my academic performance.				
D. Social Motivation - ^{raise achievement / desire to become} more successful				
1. I was able to share learning experiences with other students.				
2. I increased my contact with my fellow students in helping me throughout the subject.				
3. It is important to me to be able to ^{I always} express my feelings without offending others.				
4. It is important to me to ^I spend time with people who know about the topics that I know very little about.				
5. It is important to me to socialize ^{I prefer} with knowledgeable people.				

II. Students' Evaluation on the teachers' feedback skills

A. Constructive Feedback	4	3	2	1
1. My teachers feedback ^{to my teacher} allows me to know if I am doing well and what I could or need to do ^{and} to do even better.				
2. My teacher ^{and} provides feedback as soon as I am done ^{have helpful comment when} in my performance task.				
3. My teacher ensure privacy when giving feedback ^{regarding} about my negative behaviors.				
4. My teachers feedback is focus on my performance and not to my personality.				
5. My teachers feedback is delivered in a kind and friendly way, so it is easy for me to understand. ^{when giving feedback.}				
B. Formal Feedback				
1. My teachers give ^{presents criteria during} a lot of notice about my performance.				
2. When my teacher is providing feedback privately, my teacher makes sure that the time is convenient for both of us. ^{scheduled it on our convenient time.}				
3. My teacher offers a quick response to my actions, ^{assess me based on my actions} what and why.				
4. My teachers give specific feedback that explains what and why. ^{during feedback.}				
5. My teacher provides suggestions for my improvement.				
C. Informal Feedback				
1. My teachers say, "Good job", when I do the task correctly. ^{positive comment}				
2. My teacher leaves a personalized note on my assignments' acknowledging my efforts and improvements along with specific positive comments.				
3. My teachers take a moment to discuss the recent project, expressing appreciation for dedication and suggesting areas for further exploration.				
4. My teachers send a brief but uplifting email to my parents sharing positive observation about my engagement in class and expressing gratitude for my enthusiasm. ^{short}				
5. My teacher gathers the students after the group activity and provides feedback, praising collaborative efforts and offering suggestions to refine our teamwork skills.				
D. Corrective Feedback				
1. My teachers clearly pointing out the specific mistake or error in my work, ensuring that I understand what needs correction. ^{identify and the}				
2. My teachers offer clear examples of how I improve.				
3. My teachers point out the areas where I showed effort and where I did well.				
4. My teacher offers a detailed explanation of the correct solution or approach, when my teacher identifies the error.				
5. My teachers provide feedback on all the mistakes in my written work.				

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
 PROVINCE OF BATANGAS
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 TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

January 24, 2024

MARIEL ANGELOU U. OLAN, LPT, MEM, MAED
 Master Teacher I
 Tanauan City Integrated High School

Madam:

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled **"Teachers' Feedbacking Skills, Students' Motivation, and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students"**.

In this regard, we are seeking your expertise in helping us validate the Self-Made questionnaire that we will use to measure the variables needed in the study. Attached here with is a copy of the questionnaire that we wish to employ in the said study. Your comments and suggestions will be highly appreciated and will be a great help to this undertaking

We are hoping for your favorable response and wholehearted consideration regarding this matter.

Thank you so much and more power.

Very truly yours,

John Erick M. Pamplona
 John Erick M. Pamplona

Kenneth M. Seda
 Kenneth M. Seda

Larina R. Gonzales
 Larina R. Gonzales

Lena R. Fajarillo
 Lena R. Fajarillo

Lorenz U. Verola
 Lorenz U. Verola
 Researchers

Noted:

MR. ROJANE F. BERNAS
 MR. ROJANE F. BERNAS
 Thesis Adviser

Approved/Remarks:

MARIEL ANGELOU U. OLAN, LPT, MEM, MAED
 MARIEL ANGELOU U. OLAN, LPT, MEM, MAED
 Master Teacher I

Questionnaire Validation Sheet

Name of Validator : MARIEL ANGELOU UMIPIG-OLAN
 Highest Educational Qualification : DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE & LITERATURE
 Position Held : MASTER TEACHER I / GUEST LECTURER
 Field of Specialization : ENGLISH LANGUAGE & LITERATURE; EDUC. MANAGEMENT
 Signature :

Directions:

A. Refer to the attached research instrument for validation.

B. Please use the Rating scale below and encircle the number that corresponds to the evaluation of each value item.

4	-	very valid	2	-	less valid
3	-	moderately valid	1	-	need for revalidation

I. Level of Academic Performance

A. General Weighted Average

Value item	I.A.1	1	2	3	<u>4</u>
------------	-------	---	---	---	----------

II. Level of Students Motivation

A. Intrinsic Motivation

Value item	II.A.1	1	2	3	<u>4</u>
	II.A.2	1	2	3	<u>4</u>
	II.A.3	1	2	3	<u>4</u>
	II.A.4	1	2	3	<u>4</u>
	II.A.5	1	2	3	<u>4</u>

B. Extrinsic Motivation

Value item	II.B.1	1	2	3	<u>4</u>
	II.B.2	1	2	3	<u>4</u>

	II.B.3	1	2	3	④
	II.B.4	1	2	3	④
	II.B.5	1	2	3	④
C. Fear Motivation					
Value Item	II.C.1	1	2	3	④
	II.C.2	1	2	3	④
	II.C.3	1	2	3	④
	II.C.4	1	2	3	④
	II.C.5	1	2	3	④
D. Social Motivation					
Value Item	II.D.1	1	2	3	④
	II.D.2	1	2	3	④
	II.D.3	1	2	3	④
	II.D.4	1	2	3	④
	II.D.5	1	2	3	④
III. Students evaluation of teachers feedbacking skills					
A. Constructive Feedback					
Value Item	III.A.1	1	2	3	④
	III.A.2	1	2	3	④
	III.A.3	1	2	3	④
	III.A.4	1	2	3	④
	III.A.5	1	2	3	④
B. Formal Feedback					
Value Item	III.B.1	1	2	3	④
	III.B.2	1	2	3	④
	III.B.3	1	2	3	④
	III.B.4	1	2	3	④
	III.B.5	1	2	3	④

C. Informal Feedback

Value item

III.C.1	1	2	3	4
III.C.2	1	2	3	4
III.C.3	1	2	3	4
III.C.4	1	2	3	4
III.C.5	1	2	3	4

D. Corrective Feedback

Value item

III.D.1	1	2	3	4
III.D.2	1	2	3	4
III.D.3	1	2	3	4
III.D.4	1	2	3	4
III.D.5	1	2	3	4

Remarks/Recommendation

- kindly adhere on all the revisions / suggestions indicated in the paper. :)

Overall Rating

Please check (√) appropriate rating.

- Approved to be used as presented
- Approved to be used with revisions as indicated
- Disapproved, the researchers must make another questionnaire

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

School of Education

Dear Respondents,

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled **“Teachers’ Feedbacking Skills, Student’s Motivation and, Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High Students”**.

We will ensure the confidentiality and consent of the respondents; the researchers will provide you with all the necessary information about the study and its objectives. Thank you and may God bless you.

The Researchers *Can cut the back*

Name: _____ Age: _____

Grade level: _____

PART I. Demographic Profile

1. What is your General Weighted Average in the First (1st) Semestral Grading? _____

PART II. Level of MOTIVATION OF THE STUDENTS

Directions: The following are set of indicators that will describe the evaluation of *the students’* **teachers’ feedback skills and the level of your motivation** as a student. Using the 4-point scale shown below, indicate the degree of your agreement and disagreement in the following statement indicators of the variables described below. All responses that will be gathered by this research shall be treated with confidentiality. *Please put a check mark on the column that corresponds to your answer. Be guided by the following 4-point scale:*

4- Strongly Agree 3- Agree 2- Disagree 1- Strongly Disagree

I. Level of Motivation of the Students

	4	3	2	1
A. Intrinsic Motivation				
1. I enjoy all my subject in school. ✓				
2. I am ^{excel} good at any activity. ✓				
3. I felt competent after doing the performance task. ✓				
4. It is important to me to do well in each task in school. - I find it necessary to perform well on every task in school. ✓				
5. I am teaching myself because it feels good to learn. ✓				
B. Extrinsic Motivation				
1. I am studying to finish my study. ✓				
2. I study to avoid consequences from my parents and teachers. ✓				
3. I am doing my homework because all the ^{tasks} assignments are graded. ✓				
4. I am doing my academic performance better to have higher ^{better} grades. ✓				
5. I make my school tasks great to receive praise from teachers. - I work hard on my schoolwork to receive praise from teachers. ✓				
C. Fear Motivation				
1. I pay close attention in class and participate actively ^{so as not to be told badly.} to avoid receiving negative feedback. ✓				
2. Failing grades encourage me to study hard. I work hard in my studies to avoid fail low grades. ✓				
3. I sometimes focus on what is wrong and what I could go wrong. ✓				

4. Failure plays in shaping my aspirations to learn something. /				
5. I was driven by my desires because I don't want to be embarrassed. /				
D. Social Motivation				
1. I was able to share learning experiences with other students. /				
2. I increased my contact with my fellow students in helping myself more throughout the subject.				
3. I always express my feelings without offending others. /				
4. I spend time with people who know about the topics that I know very little about. /				
5. I prefer socializing with knowledgeable people.				

PART III.

II. Students' Evaluation on the teachers' feedback skills

Direction: The following statements show students' evaluation on the teachers' feedback skills. Please put check mark on the column that corresponds to your answer.

A. Constructive Feedback	4	3	2	1
1. My teacher allows me to know if I am doing well, what I could or need to do and to do even better. /				
2. My teacher has helpful comment when I am done with my performance task. /				
3. My teacher ensure privacy regarding negative behaviors. /				
4. My teacher focus on my performance and not to my personality. /				
5. My teachers is kind and friendly way when giving feedback. /				
B. Formal Feedback				
1. My teachers present criteria during performance. /				
2. When providing feedback, my teacher scheduled it on our convenient time. /				
3. My teacher assesses me based on my actions. /				
4. My teachers explain what and why during feedbacking. /				
5. My teacher provides suggestions for improvement. /				
C. Informal Feedback				
1. My teachers say positive comment when I do the task correctly. /				
2. My teacher leaves personalized note on my assignments acknowledging my efforts. /				
3. My teachers take a moment to express appreciation for dedication and suggesting areas for further exploration. /				
4. My teachers send short but uplifting email to my parents about my engagement in class expressing gratitude for my enthusiasm. /				
5. My teacher provides feedback, praising collaborative efforts and offering suggestions to our teamwork skills. /				
D. Corrective Feedback				
1. My teachers identify the error in my work, ensuring that I understand what needs correction. /				
2. My teachers offer clear examples of how I improve. /				
3. My teachers point out the areas where I showed effort and where I did well. /				
4. My teacher offers a detailed explanation of the correct solution or approach, when my teacher identifies the error. /				
5. My teachers provide feedback on all the mistakes in my written work. /				

Dear Respondents,
 The undersigned are presently conducting a research entitled, "teachers' Feedbacking Skills, students Motivation and Academic Performance of the selected Senior High Students".
 In line with this, may I request of your time to fully and honestly accomplish the questionnaire attached herewith. Rest assured that your responses will be treated with full confidentiality. Your cooperation will greatly contribute to the study at hand. Thank you very much.
 The Researching

APPENDIX B: Research Instrument

Dear Respondents,

The undersigned are presently conducting research entitled, "Teachers' Feedbacking Skills, Students' Motivation, and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students".

In line with this, may I request of your time to fully and honestly accomplish the questionnaire attached herewith. Rest assured that your responses will be treated with full confidentiality. Your cooperation will greatly contribute to the study at hands Thank You very much.

The Researchers

Part I. Demographic Profile

Name: _____

Age: _____

Grade level/Section: _____

1. What is your General Weighted Average in the First (1st) Semestral Grading? _____

Part II. Level of Motivation of the Students

Direction: The following statements describe the evaluation of the students' level of motivation. Please put a check mark on the column that corresponds to your answer. Be guided by the following 4-point scale.

4- Strongly Agree 3- Agree 2- Disagree 1- Strongly Disagree

A. Intrinsic Motivation	4	3	2	1
1. I like to learn from different subject.				
2. I make sure to do better at any activity.				
3. I felt competent after doing the performance task.				
4. I find it necessary to perform well on every task in school.				
5. I am teaching myself because it feels good to learn.				
B. Extrinsic Motivation				
1. I am studying to finish my study.				
2. I study to avoid consequences from my parents and teachers.				
3. I am doing my homework because all the tasks are graded.				
4. I improve my academic performance to achieve higher grades.				
5. I work hard on my schoolwork to receive praise from teachers.				
C. Fear Motivation				
1. I pay close attention in class and participate actively to avoid negative feedback.				

2. I work hard in my studies to avoid low grades.				
3. I sometimes focus on what is wrong and what I could go wrong.				
4. Failure plays in shaping my aspirations to learn something.				
5. I was driven by my desires because I don't want to be embarrassed.				
D. Social Motivation				
1. I was able to share my knowledge with my classmates.				
2. I increased communication with my fellow students in helping myself more throughout the subject.				
3. I make sure to express my emotions without offending others.				
4. I ask my classmates about the topics that I know very little about.				
5. I like interacting socially with knowledgeable people.				

Part III. Students' Evaluation on the teachers' feedback skills

Direction: The following statements show students' evaluation on the teachers' feedback skills. Please put mark on the column that corresponds to your answer.

A. Constructive Feedback	4	3	2	1
1. My teacher makes sure that I know what I need to do to improve.				
2. My teacher has insightful feedback when I am done with my performance task.				
3. My teacher ensure privacy regarding negative behaviors.				
4. My teacher focus on my performance and not to my personality.				
5. My teachers are calm when giving feedback.				
B. Formal Feedback				
1. My teachers present rubrics/criteria during performance.				
2. My teachers provide feedback in our free time.				
3. My teacher assesses my performance based on what I do.				
4. My teachers provide explanation for both what and why during feedback sessions.				
5. My teacher gives recommendations to enhance my academic performance.				
C. Informal Feedback				
1. My teachers provide positive feedback when I complete the task correctly.				
2. My teacher leaves personalized note on my tasks acknowledging my efforts.				
3. My teachers take a moment to acknowledge my dedication in studying and give suggestion on how I improve.				
4. My teachers tell my parents about how I perform in the class.				
5. My teacher provides feedback, praising collaborative efforts and offering suggestions to our teamwork skills.				
D. Corrective Feedback				
1. My teachers identify the error in my work, ensuring that I understand what needs correction.				
2. My teachers provide clear examples of how I improve.				
3. My teachers point out the areas where I showed effort and where I did well.				
4. My teacher offers a detailed explanation of the correct solution or approach, when he/she identifies the error.				
5. My teachers provide feedback on all the mistakes in my written work.				

APPENDIX C: Result of T-Test

VALIDITY TEST

VALIDITY TEST RESULT

RESEARCH TITLE:	TEACHERS' FEEDBACKING SKILLS, STUDENTS' MOTIVATION, AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THE SELECTED SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS
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To test the validity of the questionnaire, the statistician utilized **Pearson's r Correlation**. According to Ahrens et al. (2020), to assess construct validity, Pearson's correlation can be employed. Pearson's correlation is commonly used to verify the intensity of the existing linear association between variables, and it measures the linear association between quantitative variables.

The table below shows the critical values for Pearson's r . This table will be used as reference to interpret the significance of each variables/indicator to come up with an interpretation.

Table for Critical values of Pearson's r

<i>For a two-tailed test</i>				
df:	0.1	0.05	0.02	0.01
1	.988	.997	.9995	.9999
2	.9	.95	.98	.99
3	.805	.878	.934	.959
4	.729	.811	.882	.917
5	.669	.754	.833	.874
6	.622	.707	.789	.834
7	.582	.666	.75	.798
8	.549	.632	.716	.765
9	.521	.602	.685	.735
10	.497	.576	.658	.708
11	.476	.553	.634	.684
12	.458	.532	.612	.661
13	.441	.514	.592	.641
14	.426	.497	.574	.623
15	.412	.482	.558	.606
16	.4	.468	.542	.59
17	.389	.456	.528	.575
18	.378	.444	.516	.561
19	.369	.433	.503	.549
20	.36	.423	.492	.537
21	.352	.413	.482	.526
22	.344	.404	.472	.515
23	.337	.396	.462	.505
24	.33	.388	.453	.496
25	.323	.381	.445	.487
26	.317	.374	.437	.479
27	.311	.367	.43	.471
28	.306	.361	.423	.463
29	.301	.355	.416	.456
30	.296	.349	.409	.449

Using this table as reference, calculating the degrees of freedom where $30 - N = 28$, we compare the computed p value to the critical values in the Pearson's r table. To interpret the test as valid, $p > df$, where the df is 28, with a 95% confidence (0.05).

The following are the results of the validity test using Pearson's r Coefficient to test the construct validity of each indicator in the research question.

For the second test, the statistician utilized the Pearson's r Coefficient to test the convergent and discriminant validity of the indicators.

FM4	Pearson Correlation	.287	.196	.130	.196	.407	-.235	-.224	.389	-.314	-.035	.174	.431	.111	.365	.237	.533
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.124	.410	.493	.301	.026	.211	.234	.034	.091	.853	.357	.018	.559	.047	.208	.002
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
FM5	Pearson Correlation	.075	0.000	0.000	.280	.269	-.199	-.053	.211	-.267	.243	.206	.224	.323	.299	.299	.593
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.695	1.000	1.000	.135	.151	.291	.780	.264	.153	.195	.274	.234	.082	.109	.108	.001
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
SM1	Pearson Correlation	.097	0.000	.242	.363	.349	.194	-.341	.091	-.278	-.158	0.000	0.000	-.126	0.000	-.078	.313
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.610	1.000	.198	.049	.059	.305	.199	.632	.138	.405	1.000	1.000	.508	1.000	.683	.093
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
SM2	Pearson Correlation	.363	.175	.138	.453	.312	.179	.084	.297	-.090	.129	.153	.269	.321	.269	.051	.649
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.048	.356	.467	.012	.093	.344	.658	.111	.634	.498	.420	.151	.083	.151	.791	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
SM3	Pearson Correlation	.400	.553	.295	.386	.131	-.024	.323	.171	.299	.197	.201	.145	.142	.145	.233	.588
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.028	.002	.114	.035	.491	.899	.082	.366	.108	.296	.287	.443	.455	.443	.215	.001
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
SM4	Pearson Correlation	.051	.110	-.064	.064	.184	-.034	-.151	.160	-.037	-.046	.047	.034	-.096	-.051	-.218	.291
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.788	.563	.738	.738	.331	.858	.424	.398	.848	.808	.805	.858	.615	.788	.246	.119
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
SM5	Pearson Correlation	.198	.020	.302	.384	.449	.161	-.143	.345	-.326	.060	.233	.352	.073	.132	.153	.620
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.294	.915	.105	.036	.013	.394	.449	.062	.079	.754	.215	.056	.701	.486	.420	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
CF1	Pearson Correlation	.153	.161	.082	.327	.419	.117	.259	.274	.073	.237	.494	.284	.485	.284	.339	.548
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.419	.395	.667	.077	.021	.539	.167	.143	.701	.206	.006	.128	.007	.128	.067	.002
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
CF2	Pearson Correlation	.565	.558	.146	.219	.398	.534	.190	.490	.200	.265	.207	.508	.318	.312	-.021	.643
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.001	.441	.245	.029	.002	.428	.006	.289	.157	.273	.004	.087	.093	.913	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
CF3	Pearson Correlation	-.089	.185	-.028	.167	.280	.208	.237	.314	.064	.363	.277	.200	.328	.200	.143	.435
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.640	.329	.884	.379	.134	.270	.206	.091	.738	.049	.138	.288	.077	.288	.452	.016
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
CF4	Pearson Correlation	.252	.232	.314	.314	.201	.112	.080	.289	.080	.365	.193	.168	.169	.420	.179	.513
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.179	.217	.091	.091	.286	.556	.676	.121	.674	.048	.306	.375	.371	.021	.343	.004
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
CF5	Pearson Correlation	.359	.313	.174	.448	.275	.359	.130	.626	-.019	.054	.285	.439	.176	.439	.197	.610
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.051	.093	.357	.013	.141	.051	.493	.000	.920	.776	.127	.015	.354	.015	.296	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
POSTTEST	Pearson Correlation	.434	.499	.248	.501	.477	.196	.372	.692	.181	.425	.450	.456	.520	.518	.384	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.017	.005	.186	.000	.008	.299	.043	.000	.339	.019	.013	.011	.003	.003	.031	
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

CONVERGENT AND DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY TEST RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

STUDENTS MOTIVATION

		Correlations																				
		IM1	IM2	IM3	IM4	IM5	EM1	EM2	EM3	EM4	EM5	FM1	FM2	FM3	FM4	FM5	SM1	SM2	SM3	SM4	SM5	
IM1	Pearson	1																				
	Correlation		-.041	.228	.301	.028	.238	-.021	.148	.333	-.045	.089	-.033	.000	-.020	.228	.296	.266	.111	-.104	.269	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.830	.225	.106	.881	.205	.912	.435	.072	.815	.640	.861	1.000	.917	.225	.112	.156	.559	.584	.150	
IM2	Pearson		1																			
	Correlation	-.041		.370*	.241	.517**	.234	.083	.218	.246	.121	.307	.077	.092	.160	.000	.073	.083	-.027	.218	.237	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.830		.044	.000	.003	.213	.664	.246	.190	.525	.099	.687	.630	.398	1.000	.702	.663	.886	.248	.207	
IM3	Pearson			1																		
	Correlation	.228	.370*		.556**	.493**	.455*	.307	.676**	.558**	.347	.528**	.352	.227	.463**	.555**	.135	.419*	.490**	.135	.454*	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.225	.044		.001	.006	.011	.098	.000	.001	.061	.003	.056	.228	.010	.001	.476	.021	.006	.478	.012	
IM4	Pearson				1																	
	Correlation	.301	.241	.556**		.365*	.327	.236	.237	.401*	.054	.518**	.330	.187	.171	.274	.119	.310	.200	.230	.396*	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.106	.200	.001		.047	.077	.209	.206	.028	.778	.003	.075	.323	.368	.142	.532	.096	.288	.222	.031	
IM5	Pearson					1																
	Correlation	.028	.517**	.493**	.365*		.186	.086	.455*	.398*	.145	.319	.365*	.286	.252	.389*	.253	.354	.398*	.293	.218	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.881	.003	.006	.047		.326	.650	.012	.029	.445	.085	.047	.125	.180	.033	.178	.055	.029	.116	.247	
EM1	Pearson						1															
	Correlation	.238	.234	.455*	.327	.186		.292	.242	.544**	-.018	.491**	.327	.114	.521**	.280	.121	.158	.159	.170	.522**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.205	.213	.011	.077	.326		.117	.198	.002	.924	.006	.077	.548	.003	.135	.524	.405	.402	.369	.003	
EM2	Pearson							1														
	Correlation	-.021	.083	.307	.236	.086	.292		.449*	.168	.485**	.214	.574**	-.141	.242	.288	-.075	.134	.126	.342	.221	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.912	.664	.098	.209	.650	.117		.013	.374	.007	.257	.001	.457	.198	.122	.694	.480	.506	.064	.241	
EM3	Pearson								1													
	Correlation	.148	.218	.676**	.237	.455*	.242	.449*		.296	.437*	.158	.475*	.298	.531**	.568**	.053	.300	.395*	.139	.538**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.435	.246	.000	.206	.012	.198	.013		.112	.016	.403	.008	.110	.003	.001	.782	.107	.031	.465	.002	
EM4	Pearson									1												
	Correlation	.333	.246	.558**	.401*	.398*	.544**	.168	.296		.223	.445*	.535**	.000	.279	.548**	.415*	.531**	.333	.156	.471**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.072	.190	.001	.028	.029	.002	.374	.112		.235	.014	.002	1.000	.135	.002	.023	.003	.072	.410	.009	
EM5	Pearson										1											
	Correlation	-.045	.121	.347	.054	.145	-.018	.485**	.437*	.223		.096	.322	.075	.166	.245	.119	.382*	.343	.272	.243	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.815	.525	.061	.778	.445	.924	.007	.016	.235		.616	.082	.694	.382	.192	.531	.037	.064	.146	.195	
FM1	Pearson											1										
	Correlation	.089	.307	.528**	.518**	.319	.491**	.214	.158	.445*	.096		.250	.224	.416*	.427*	.158	.400*	.356	.362*	.413*	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.640	.099	.003	.003	.085	.006	.257	.403	.014	.616		.183	.234	.022	.019	.403	.029	.053	.050	.023	
FM2	Pearson												1									
	Correlation	-.033	.077	.352	.330	.365*	.327	.574**	.475**	.535**	.322	.250		.299	.490**	.457*	.356	.503**	.200	.230	.530**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.861	.687	.056	.075	.047	.077	.001	.008	.002	.082	.183		.109	.006	.011	.053	.005	.288	.222	.003	
FM3	Pearson													1								
	Correlation	.000	.092	.227	.187	.286	.114	-.141	.298	.000	.075	.224	.299*		.423*	.230	.497*	.405	.280	.175	.489**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	1.000	.630	.228	.323	.125	.548	.457	.110	1.000	.694	.234	.109		.020	.222	.005	.026	.135	.356	.006	
FM4	Pearson														1							
	Correlation	-.020	.160	.463**	.171	.252	.521**	.242	.531**	.279	.166	.416*	.490**	.423*		.546**	.248	.329	.186	.044	.625**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.917	.398	.010	.368	.180	.003	.198	.003	.135	.382	.022	.006	.020		.002	.186	.076	.325	.819	.000	
FM5	Pearson															1						
	Correlation	.225	1.000	.001	.142	.033	.135	.122	.001	.002	.192	.019	.011	.222	.002		.080	.003	.011	.452	.010	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.30		.30	.30	.30	.30	.30	.30	.30	.30	.30	.30	.30	.30		.30	.30	.30	.30	.30	
SM1	Pearson																1					
	Correlation	.296	.073	.135	.119	.253	.121	-.075	.053	.415*	.119	.158	.356	.497*	.248	.324		.729**	.197	.231	.418*	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.112	.702	.476	.532	.178	.524	.694	.782	.023	.531	.403	.053	.005	.186	.080		.000	.296	.219	.021	
SM2	Pearson																	1				
	Correlation	.266	.083	.419*	.310	.354	.158	.134	.300	.531**	.382*	.400*	.503**	.405*	.329	.529**	.729**		.418*	.249	.477**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.156	.663	.021	.096	.055	.405	.480	.107	.003	.037	.029	.005	.026	.076	.003	.000		.021	.185	.008	
SM3	Pearson																		1			
	Correlation	.111	-.027	.490**	.200	.398*	.159	.126	.395*	.333	.343	.356	.200	.280	.186	.456*	.197	.418*		.1	.191	.179
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.559	.886	.006	.288	.029	.402	.506	.031	.072	.064	.053	.288	.135	.325	.011	.296	.021		.312	.343	.303
SM4	Pearson																			1		
	Correlation	-.104	.218	.135	.230	.293	.170	.342	.139	.156	.272	.362*	.230	.175	.044	.143	.231	.249	.191	.1	.200	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.584	.248	.478	.222	.116	.369	.064	.465	.410	.146	.050	.222	.356	.819	.452	.219	.185	.312	.290	.290	
SM5	Pearson																				1	
	Correlation	.269	.237	.454*	.396*	.218	.522**	.221	.538**	.471**	.243	.413*	.530**	.489**	.625**	.461*	.418*	.477**	.179	.200	.1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.150	.207	.012	.031	.247	.003	.241	.002	.009	.195	.023	.003	.006	.000	.010	.021	.008	.343	.290	.290	

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

TEACHERS' FEEDBACKING SKILLS

		Correlations																				
		CF1	CF2	CF3	CF4	CF5	FF1	FF2	FF3	FF4	FF5	IF1	IF2	IF3	IF4	IF5	COF1	COF2	COF3	COF4	COF5	
CF1	Pearson	1	.470*	.055	.274	.106	.153	.161	.082	.327	.419*	.117	.259	.274	.073	.237	.494*	.284	.486*	.284	.339	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.009	.775	.143	.577	.419	.395	.667	.077	.021	.539	.167	.143	.701	.206	.006	.128	.007	.128	.067	.067
N		30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
CF2	Pearson	.470*	1	.341	.398*	.353	.566*	.558*	.146	.219	.398*	.534*	.150	.490*	.200	.265	.207	.508*	.318	.312	.021	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.009	.065	.029	.056	.001	.001	.441	.245	.029	.002	.428	.006	.289	.157	.273	.004	.087	.093	.913
N			30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
CF3	Pearson	.055	.341	1	.524*	.324	-.089	.185	-.028	.167	.280	.208	.237	.314	.064	.363*	.277	.200	.328	.200	.143	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.775	.065	.003	.081	.640	.329	.884	.379	.134	.270	.206	.091	.738	.049	.138	.288	.077	.288	.452	.452
N				30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
CF4	Pearson	.274	.398*	.524*	1	.344	.252	.232	.314	.314	.201	.112	.080	.289	.080	.365*	.193	.168	.169	.420*	.179	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.143	.029	.003	.063	.179	.217	.091	.091	.286	.556	.676	.121	.674	.048	.306	.375	.371	.021	.343	.343
N					30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
CF5	Pearson	.143	.029	.003	.063	1	.359	.313	.174	.448*	.275	.359	.130	.626*	-.019	.054	.285	.439*	.176	.439*	.197	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.106	.353	.324	.344	.359	.313	.174	.448*	.275	.359	.130	.626*	-.019	.054	.285	.439*	.176	.439*	.197	.197
N						30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
FF1	Pearson	.577	.056	.081	.063	.359	1	.642**	.089	.245	.064	.286	.000	.252	.179	.097	-.025	.339	.031	.161	-.243	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.153	.566*	.089	.252	.359	.642**	.089	.245	.064	.286	.000	.252	.179	.097	-.025	.339	.031	.161	-.243	-.243
N																						
FF2	Pearson	.419	.001	.640	.179	.051	.642**	1	.000	.640	.192	.736	.126	1.000	.179	.344	.610	.897	.067	.871	.396	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.419	.001	.640	.179	.051	.642**	.000	.640	.192	.736	.126	1.000	.179	.344	.610	.897	.067	.871	.396	.396
N																						
FF3	Pearson	.161	.558*	.185	.232	.313	.642**	1	.226	.287	.089	.285	.351	.387	.483**	.268	.136	.181	.114	.099	.092	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.395	.001	.329	.217	.093	.000	.231	.124	.641	.127	.057	.035	.007	.152	.472	.339	.549	.604	.628	.628
N																						
FF4	Pearson	.082	.146	-.028	.314	.174	.089	.226	1	.111	.320	-.059	.079	.209	.016	.121	.031	.022	-.135	.245	.214	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.667	.441	.884	.091	.357	.640	.231	.559	.084	.755	.678	.267	.933	.524	.872	.907	.477	.192	.256	.256
N																						
FF5	Pearson	.327	.219	.167	.314	.448*	.245	.287	.111	1	.280	.208	.396*	.209	.143	.242	.431*	.089	.231	.312	.321	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.077	.245	.379	.091	.013	.192	.124	.559	.134	.270	.030	.267	.449	.198	.017	.640	.219	.093	.084	.084
N																						
IF1	Pearson	.419	.398*	.280	.201	.275	.064	.089	.320	.280	1	.171	-.038	.352	-.084	.000	.650**	.257	.342	.257	.197	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.021	.029	.134	.286	.141	.736	.641	.084	.134	.366	.842	.056	.658	1.000	.000	.171	.064	.171	.297	
N																						
IF2	Pearson	.117	.534*	.208	.112	.359	.286	.285	-.059	.208	.171	1	.127	.224	.136	.065	.099	.190	.237	-.048	-.172	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.539	.002	.270	.556	.051	.126	.127	.755	.270	.366	.504	.234	.473	.734	.604	.313	.208	.803	.365	
N																						
IF3	Pearson	.259	.150	.237	.080	.130	.000	.351	.079	.396*	-.038	.127	1	.318	.530**	.448*	.292	.000	.558*	.317	.474*	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.167	.428	.206	.676	.493	1.000	.057	.678	.030	.842	.504	.087	.003	.013	.117	1.000	.001	.088	.008	
N																						
IF4	Pearson	.274	.490*	.314	.289	.626*	.252	.387	.209	.209	.352	.224	.318	1	.200	.365*	.193	.588**	.533*	.588**	.381*	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.143	.006	.091	.121	.000	.179	.035	.267	.267	.056	.234	.087	.289	.048	.306	.001	.002	.001	.038	
N																						
IF5	Pearson	.073	.200	.064	.080	-.019	.179	.483*	.016	.143	-.084	.136	.530**	.200	1	.416*	.135	.013	.291	.013	.140	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.701	.289	.738	.674	.920	.344	.007	.933	.449	.658	.473	.003	.289	.022	.476	.947	.119	.947	.461	
N																						
COF1	Pearson	.237	.265	.363*	.365*	.054	.097	.268	.121	.242	.000	.065	.448*	.365*	.416*	1	.000	.000	.294	.194	.000	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.206	.157	.049	.048	.776	.610	.152	.524	.198	1.000	.734	.013	.048	.022	1.000	1.000	.115	.305	1.000	
N																						
COF2	Pearson	.494*	.207	.277	.193	.285	-.025	.136	.031	.431*	.650**	.099	.292	.193	.135	.000	1	.148	.526**	.271	.501**	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.006	.273	.138	.306	.127	.897	.472	.872	.017	.000	.604	.117	.306	.476	1.000	.435	.003	.147	.005	
N																						
COF3	Pearson	.284	.508*	.200	.168	.439*	.339	.181	.022	.089	.257	.190	.000	.588**	.013	.000	.148	1	.510**	.643**	.243	
	Correlation																					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.128	.004	.288	.375	.015	.067	.339	.907	.640	.171	.313	1.000	.001	.947	1.000	.435	.004	.000	.196	
N																						
COF4	Pearson	.486*	.318	.328	.169	.176	.031	.114	-.135	.231	.342	.237	.558**	.533**	.291	.294	.					

RELIABILITY TEST

RESEARCH TITLE:	TEACHERS' FEEDBACKING SKILLS, STUDENTS' MOTIVATION, AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THE SELECTED SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS
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To test the reliability of the questionnaire, the statistician tested the *INTERNAL CONSISTENCY* of the instrument using **Cronbach's Alpha** and the instrument's *TEST-RETEST CORRELATION* using **Pearson Product-Moment Correlation**. According to Collins (2007), Cronbach's Alpha is a way of assessing reliability by comparing the amount of shared variance, or covariance, among the items making up an instrument to the amount of overall variance. The table below shows the interpretation of Cronbach's Alpha.

INTERPRETATION	
Cronbach's Alpha	Internal Consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

The following are the results of the reliability test.

INTERNAL CONSISTENCY TEST

Cronbach's Alpha

RELIABILITY STATISTICS	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.897	40

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
IMP1	135.2000	115.062	.319	.896
IMP2	135.5667	117.082	.261	.896
IMP3	135.4333	109.909	.703	.890
IMP4	135.2667	111.789	.547	.893
IMP5	135.2667	111.582	.513	.893
EMP1	135.0667	114.064	.403	.895
EMP2	135.3333	113.816	.306	.897
EMP3	135.0000	110.690	.809	.890
EMP4	135.1667	112.213	.500	.893
EMP5	135.4667	110.533	.459	.894
FMP1	135.5000	107.983	.624	.891
FMP2	135.0000	113.862	.494	.894
FMP3	135.3000	111.045	.615	.892
FMP4	135.1333	109.913	.538	.892

FMP5	135.4000	106.248	.734	.888
SMP1	135.0667	116.892	.168	.898
SMP2	135.2667	112.616	.481	.893
SMP3	135.2333	109.702	.706	.890
SMP4	135.2000	114.924	.267	.897
SMP5	135.1333	111.499	.555	.892
CFP1	135.2000	114.372	.431	.894
CFP2	135.1000	115.334	.294	.896
CFP3	135.0667	117.306	.134	.898
CFP4	135.1667	114.764	.277	.897
CFP5	134.9000	114.024	.526	.894
FFP1	134.8667	117.292	.158	.898
FFP2	135.0333	113.137	.486	.894
FFP3	135.2333	117.840	.110	.898
FFP4	135.0000	115.310	.354	.895
FFP5	134.8667	113.568	.602	.893
IFP1	134.8667	120.257	-.124	.900
IFP2	135.3667	116.792	.121	.900
IFP3	135.1333	115.430	.286	.896
IFP4	135.4333	111.702	.435	.894
IFP5	135.0333	112.171	.650	.892
COFP1	135.0000	118.414	.058	.899
COFP2	134.9667	116.930	.173	.898
COFP3	135.0667	114.271	.345	.896
COFP4	135.0667	115.030	.322	.896
COFP5	135.3333	112.023	.394	.895

Interpretation: $\alpha = .897$ therefore its reliability is interpreted as **GOOD where $0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$**

TEST-RETEST CORRELATION
Test of Stability
Pearson Product-Moment Correlation

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
PRETEST	135.4333	11.65801	30
POSTTEST	138.6333	10.92130	30

Correlations

		PRETEST	POSTTEST
PRETEST	Pearson Correlation	1	.748**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	30	30
POSTTEST	Pearson Correlation	.748**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	30	30

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table above shows the result of correlation between the respondents' pretest and post-test responses. With a p value of 0.748 and an r value of <0.01.

Interpretation

There is A significant relationship between the respondents' pretest and the posttest responses, therefore, the instrument's coefficient of stability is **RELIABLE**.

APPENDIX D: Letter for Distribution and Letter of Approval

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
 PROVINCE OF BATANGAS
 CITY GOVERNMENT OF TANAUAN
 TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

January 25, 2024

LOURDES T. BERMUDEZ, CESO VI
 Schools Division Superintendent
 DepEd, Tanauan City Division

Ma'am;

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled, "**Teachers' Feedbacking Skills, Students' Motivation, and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students**"

In this regards, we are seeking your permission to distribute the attached validated questionnaires to the Senior High School students of Tanauan School of Fisheries reliability testing and final data gathering.

Rest assured that the data to be obtained will be treated with utmost confidentiality and the result of the study will be submitted to the above-mentioned schools to contribute for its betterment.

Your permission will be of great contribution to the success of this undertaking. Thank you so much and more power.

Very truly yours,

[Signature]
John Erick M. Pamplona

[Signature]
Kenneth M. Seda

[Signature]
Larina R. Gonzales

[Signature]
Lenis R. Parayillo

[Signature]
Lorenz U. Verola
 The Researchers

Noted:

[Signature]
IMELDA Y. MAGPANTAY, LPT, PhD
 Research Director

[Signature]
JASCÉLYNN N. OLIMPIADA, LPT, PhD
 Dean, School of Education / VP for Academic Affairs

[Signature]
MARCIAL V. GOGUANCO, JR.
 Officer-in-Charge

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
REGION IV - A CALABARZON
CITY SCHOOLS DIVISION OF TANAUAN

CN 2024 - 0216

25 January 2024

JOHN ERICK M. PAMPLONA, et.al.
Researchers
Tanauan City College
Tanauan City, Batangas

Dear Mr. Pamplona:

Greetings of health and safety!

This is in connection with your letter dated January 25, 2024, regarding your request to distribute questionnaires to the Senior High School students of Tanauan School of Fisheries of this city schools division.

Relative to this, permission is granted provided that **DepEd Order No. 9 s. 2005, Instituting Measures on Time – On – Task and Data Privacy Act of 2012** will be strictly observed.

Lastly, to fulfill our vision of continuous improvement for better service delivery, we request that you provide this office an e-copy of your findings and recommendations.

Yours truly,

LOURDES T. BERMUDEZ, CESO V
Schools Division Superintendent

Address: Pres.J.P. Laurel Highway, Poblacion 1, Tanauan City, Batangas 4232
Telephone No.: (043) 723-9015 / 723-9277 / 784-4788 / 403-9363
Email Address: tanauan.city@deped.gov.ph
Website: <https://depedtanauacity.com>

Mapusong paglingkod,
liwanag at pag-asa ng kabataan;
Angat Tanauan!

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
 PROVINCE OF BATANGAS
 CITY GOVERNMENT OF TANAUAN
 TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

February 2, 2024

Shirley C. Siman, PhD
 Vocational School Administrator III
 Tanauan School of Fisheries

Thru: **NELDA V. ALMENDRAS**
 Head teacher VI
 Officer In Charge Assistant Senior High School Principal
 Tanauan School of Fisheries

Madam:

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled "**Teachers' Feedbacking Skills, Students' Motivation, and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students**".

In this regard, we are seeking your permission to distribute the attached questionnaire to the Selected Senior High School students. Your permission will be of great contribution to the success of this undertaking. Rest assured that the answers will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Thank you so much and more power.

Very truly yours,

John Erick M. Pamplona

Kenneth M. Seda

Larisa R. Gonzales

Lenie R. Pajarillo

Lorenz U. Verola

Researchers

Noted:

MR. ROJANE F. BERNAS
 Thesis Adviser

Approved/Remarks:

Shirley C. Siman, PhD
 Vocational School Administrator III

APPENDIX E: Distribution Tables, Computation of Weighted Mean

**Table A
Respondents of the Study**

Grade Level	Population size	Sample size
Grade 11	118	74
Grade 12	119	75
Total	237	149

**Table B
Interpretation of Mean Ranges**

Numerical Value	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretations
4	4.00-3.25	Strongly Agree
3	3.24-2.50	Agree
2	2.49-1.75	Disagree
1	1.74-1.00	Strongly Disagree

Likert Four-Point Scale Range Interpretation (Alico & Guimba, 2015)

Table 1
Academic Performance

Academic Performance	Frequency	Percentage
75-79%	2	1.3
80-84%	33	22.2
85-89%	68	45.7
90% and above	46	30.8
TOTAL	149	100

Table 2.1
Level of Motivation In terms of Intrinsic Motivation

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. I like to learn from different subject.	3.61	0.52	Strongly Agree
2. I make sure to do better at any activity.	3.52	0.55	Strongly Agree
3. I felt competent after doing the performance task.	3.34	0.61	Strongly Agree
4. I find it necessary to perform well on every task in school.	3.38	0.63	Strongly Agree
5. I am teaching myself because it feels good to learn.	3.48	0.61	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.47	0.58	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 - Agree, 2.49-1.75 - Disagree, 1.74-1.00 - Strongly Disagree

Table 2.2
Level of Motivation In terms of Extrinsic Motivation

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. I am studying to finish my study.	3.67	0.57	Strongly Agree
2. I study to avoid consequences from my parents and teachers.	3.39	0.62	Strongly Agree
3. I am doing my homework because all the tasks are graded.	3.59	0.62	Strongly Agree
4. I improve my academic performance to achieve higher grades.	3.59	0.60	Strongly Agree
5. I work hard on my schoolwork to receive praise from teachers.	3.35	0.69	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.52	0.62	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 – Agree, 2.49-1.75 – Disagree, 1.74-1.00 – Strongly Disagree

Table 2.3
Level of Motivation in terms of Fear Motivation

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. I pay close attention in class and participate actively to avoid negative feedback.	3.41	0.60	Strongly Agree
2. I work hard in my studies to avoid low grades.	3.53	0.56	Strongly Agree
3. I sometimes focus on what is wrong and what I could go wrong.	3.26	0.64	Strongly Agree
4. Failure plays in shaping my aspirations to learn something.	3.38	0.64	Strongly Agree
5. I was driven by my desires because I don't want to be embarrassed.	3.32	0.66	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.38	0.62	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 – Agree, 2.49-1.75 – Disagree, 1.74-1.00 – Strongly Disagree

Table 2.4
Level of Motivation In terms of Social Motivation

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. I was able to share my knowledge with my classmates.	3.46	0.64	Strongly Agree
2. I increased communication with my fellow students in helping myself more throughout the subject.	3.46	0.60	Strongly Agree
3. I make sure to express my emotions without offending others.	3.42	0.64	Strongly Agree
4. I ask my classmates about the topics that I know very little about.	3.50	0.63	Strongly Agree
5. I like interacting socially with knowledgeable people.	3.43	0.64	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.45	0.63	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 – Agree, 2.49-1.75 – Disagree, 1.74-1.00 – Strongly Disagree

Table 3.1
Students' Evaluation of the Teachers' Feedback Skills in terms of Constructive Feedback

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. My teacher makes sure that I know what I need to do to improve.	3.60	0.56	Strongly Agree
2. My teacher has insightful feedback when I am done with my performance task.	3.50	0.63	Strongly Agree
3. My teacher ensure privacy regarding negative behaviors.	3.46	0.66	Strongly Agree
4. My teacher focuses on my performance and not to my personality.	3.37	0.71	Strongly Agree
5. My teachers are calm when giving feedback.	3.63	0.52	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.51	0.62	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 – Agree, 2.49-1.75 – Disagree, 1.74-1.00 – Strongly Disagree

Table 3.2

Students' Evaluation of the Teachers' Feedback Skills in terms of Formal Feedback

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. My teachers present rubrics/criteria during performance.	3.66	0.55	Strongly Agree
2. My teachers provide feedback in our free time.	3.58	0.58	Strongly Agree
3. My teacher assesses my performance based on what I do.	3.56	0.60	Strongly Agree
4. My teachers provide explanation for both what and why during feedback sessions.	3.62	0.57	Strongly Agree
5. My teacher gives recommendations to enhance my academic performance.	3.64	0.54	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.61	0.57	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 – Agree, 2.49-1.75 – Disagree, 1.74-1.00 – Strongly Disagree

Table 3.3

Students' Evaluation of the Teachers' Feedback Skills in terms of Informal Feedback

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. My teachers provide positive feedback when I complete the task correctly.	3.56	0.61	Strongly Agree
2. My teacher leaves personalized note on my tasks acknowledging my efforts.	3.40	0.61	Strongly Agree
3. My teachers take a moment to acknowledge my dedication in studying and give suggestion on how I improve.	3.51	0.63	Strongly Agree
4. My teachers tell my parents about how I perform in the class.	3.40	0.69	Strongly Agree
5. My teacher provides feedback, praising collaborative efforts and offering suggestions to our teamwork skills.	3.54	0.62	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.48	0.63	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 – Agree, 2.49-1.75 – Disagree, 1.74-1.00 – Strongly Disagree

Table 3.4
Students' Evaluation of the Teachers' Feedback Skills in terms of Corrective Feedback

Indicators	M	SD	VI
1. My teachers identify the error in my work, ensuring that I understand what needs correction.	3.58	0.57	Strongly Agree
2. My teachers provide clear examples of how I improve.	3.54	0.60	Strongly Agree
3. My teachers point out the areas where I showed effort and where I did well.	3.56	0.57	Strongly Agree
4. My teacher offers a detailed explanation of the correct solution or approach, when he/she identifies the error.	3.54	0.64	Strongly Agree
5. My teachers provide feedback on all the mistakes in my written work.	3.54	0.66	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.55	0.61	Strongly Agree

M- Mean, SD- Standard Deviation, VI- Verbal Interpretation, 4.00-3.25 - Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50 – Agree, 2.49-1.75 – Disagree, 1.74-1.00 – Strongly Disagree

Table 4
Significant relationship between students' motivation and academic performance.

Variable	r value	p value	Decision (H_o)	Interpretation
Students' Motivation and Academic Performance	0.206	0.012	Reject H _o	Significant (Weak Positive Correlation)

p<0.05= Significant, p>0.05=Not significant

Table 5
Significant relationship between teachers' feedback skills and students' academic performance.

Variable	r value	p value	Decision (H ₀)	Interpretation
Teachers' Feedback Skills and Students' Academic Performance	0.194	0.018	Reject H ₀	Significant (<i>Very Weak Positive Correlation</i>)

p<0.05= Significant, *p*>0.05=Not significant

Table 6
Significant relationship between teachers' feedback skills and students' motivation

Variable	r value	p value	Decision (H ₀)	Interpretation
Teachers' Feedback Skills and Students' Motivation	0.750	< 0.01	Reject H ₀	Significant (<i>Strong Positive Correlation</i>)

p<0.05= Significant, *p*>0.05=Not significant

APPENDIX F: Computation of Significant Relationship

SOP- 4

Inferential Statistics

Computed Table A: Correlation between students' motivation and academic performance.

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
MEAN1	3.4542	.39730	149
ACAD	87.2282	3.87842	149

Correlations

		MEAN1	ACAD
MEAN1	Pearson Correlation	1	.206*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.012
	N	149	149
ACAD	Pearson Correlation	.206*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.012	
	N	149	149

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

SOP- 5

Computed Table B: Correlation between teachers' feedback skills and students' academic performance.

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
MEAN2	3.5389	.43608	149
ACAD	87.2282	3.87842	149

Correlations

		MEAN2	ACAD
MEAN2	Pearson Correlation	1	.194*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.018
	N	149	149
ACAD	Pearson Correlation	.194*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.018	
	N	149	149

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

SOP- 6

Computed Table B: Correlation between teachers' feedback skills and students' motivation.

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
MEAN1	3.4542	.39730	149
MEAN2	3.5389	.43608	149

Correlations

		MEAN1	MEAN2
MEAN1	Pearson Correlation	1	.750**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	149	149
MEAN2	Pearson Correlation	.750**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	149	149

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

CURRICULUM VITAE**GONZALES, LARIÑA R.**

257, Cale Tanauan City Batangas, 4232

Contact No.: 0907-685-0025

Email Address: larinarivera314@gmail.com

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age : 20 years old
 Gender : Female
 Date of Birth : August 13, 2003
 Place of Birth : Brgy. Cale, Tanauan City Batangas
 Height : 5'0
 Weight : 50 kg
 Civil Status : Single
 Religion : Roman Catholic
 Languages/Dialect Spoken : Tagalog and English

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary : **TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE**
 Tanauan City Batangas
 2021-present

Senior High School I: **TANAUAN INSTITUTE INC.**
 Tanauan City Batangas
 S/Y 2019-2021

Junior High School : **TANAUAN CITY INTEGRATED HIGH SCHOOL**
 Trapiche 1, Tanauan City Batangas
 S/Y 2015-2019

Primary School : **CALE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL**
 Cale Tanauan City Batangas
 S/Y 2008-2015

Lariña R. Gonzales

Applicant Signature

PAJARILLO, LENIE R.

128, Dayapan, Bilogbilog, Tanauan City, Batangas,
4232

Contact No.: 0955-354-7954

Email Address: leniepajar@gmail.com

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age	:	22 years old
Gender	:	Female
Date of Birth	:	June 13, 2001
Place of Birth	:	Bagbag 3, Tanauan City Batangas
Height	:	5'1
Weight	:	40 kg
Civil Status	:	Single
Religion	:	Roman Catholic
Languages/Dialect Spoken	:	Tagalog and English

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary	:	TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE Trapiche 1, Tanauan City Batangas 2019-present
Senior High School	:	TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE Trapiche 1, Tanauan City Batangas S/Y 2017-2019
Junior High School	:	LUYOS NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL Luyos, Tanauan City Batangas S/Y 2013-2017
Primary School	:	BILOGBILOG ELEMENTARY SCHOOL Bilogbilog, Tanauan City, Batangas S/Y 2007-2013

Lenie R. Pajarillo
Applicant Signature

PAMPLONA, JOHN ERICK M

21 Talaga, Tanauan City, Batangas, 4232

Contact No.: 0945-715-4490

Email Address: erickpamplona21@gmail.com

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age : 22 years old
 Gender : male
 Date of Birth : may 21, 2001
 Place of Birth : Sto.Tomas Batangas
 Height : 5'7
 Weight : 75 kg
 Civil Status : Single
 Religion : Roman Catholic
 Languages/Dialect Spoken: Tagalog and English

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary : **TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE**
 Trapiche 1, Tanauan City Batangas
 2019-present

Senior High School : **SAINT JOHN ACADAMY**
 Tanauan City Batangas
 S/Y 2017-2019

Junior High School : **MABINI EDUCATION INSTITUTION**
 Talaga, Tanauan City Batangas
 S/Y 2013-2017

Primary School : **TALAGA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL**
 Talaga, Tanauan City, Batangas
 S/Y 2007-2013

John Erick M. Pamplona

Applicant Signature

SEDA, KENNETH M,
 0112, Ulango Tanauan City Batangas, 4232
 Contact No.: 09352840030
 Email Address: sedakenneth28@gmail.com

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age : 21 years old
 Gender : Male
 Date of Birth : September 16, 2002
 Place of Birth : Ulango Tanauan City Batangas
 Height : 5'6
 Weight : 70 kg
 Civil Status : Single
 Religion : Roman Catholic
 Languages/Dialect Spoken : Tagalog and English

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary : **TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE**
 Tanauan City Batangas
 2021-present

Senior High School : **FISRT INDUSTRIAL SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY**
 Sta. Anastacia, Sto Tomas Batangas
 S/Y 2019-2021

Junior High School : **ULANGO INTEGRATED HIGHSCHOOL**
 Ulango, Tanauan City Batangas
 S/Y 2015-2019

Primary School : **ULANGO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL**
 Balete, Batangas
 S/Y 2009-2015

Kenneth M. Seda
 Applicant Signature

VEROLA, LORENZ U.

196, Talaga, Tanauan City Batangas, 4232

Contact No.: 09179723014

Email Address: verola0@gmail.com

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age : 21 years old
 Gender : Male
 Date of Birth : August 10, 2002
 Place of Birth : Sto. Tomas Batangas
 Height : 5'4
 Weight : 60 kg
 Civil Status : Single
 Religion : Roman Catholic
 Languages/Dialect Spoken : Tagalog and English

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary : **TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE**
 Tanauan City Batangas
 2021-present

Senior High School : **TANAUAN SCHOOL OF FISHERIES**
 Ambulong, Tanauan City, Batangas
 S/Y 2019-2021

Junior High School : **TANAUAN SCHOOL OF FISHERIES**
 Ambulong, Tanauan City Batangas
 S/Y 2015-2019

Primary School : **TALAGA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL**
 Talaga, Tanauan City, Batangas
 S/Y 2009-2015

Lorenz U. Verola
 Applicant Signature